

REGULAR PAPER

Traceable and Verifiable Software Requirements: A Synthesis of AI-Enabled Formal Methods

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Abstract

The generation of formal specifications from informal, natural language requirements remains a critical challenge in ensuring software correctness, particularly in safety-critical domains such as aerospace, autonomous systems, and medical devices. This paper presents a comprehensive survey and synthesis of recent research exploring the use of large language models (LLMs) and AI-driven techniques in the formalisation of software requirements. Drawing on an analysis of more than one hundred studies, it identifies state-of-the-art methods for translating natural language requirements into formal specifications across various programming languages and verification tools, including model checkers and theorem provers. Beyond technical methodologies, the work highlights key challenges in requirements traceability, tool integration, and specification reuse.

Complementing this survey, the paper reports an empirical evaluation of Frama-C plugins, including the Runtime Error (RTE) and Value Analysis (EVA) analysers, as well as the PathCrawler automatic test generation tool. These experiments assess the capability of formal analysis tools to infer assertions, generate ANSI/ISO C Specification Language (ACSL) annotations, detect runtime anomalies, and produce test cases for representative C programs. The study identifies practical barriers such as solver instability, path coverage constraints, and tool-specific restrictions, proposing strategies like dataset adaptation, selective path exploration, and local configuration to overcome them. The findings demonstrate that automated formalisation and verification workflows can enhance program correctness while emphasising the continued importance of human-guided intervention and coordinated multi-tool use.

KEYWORDS

Static Program Analysis, ACSL Annotation, Frama-C EVA, Runtime Error Detection, Specification Automation

1 | INTRODUCTION

Relying solely on natural language to express software requirements has long been recognised as a persistent source of ambiguity and misinterpretation. Even when written with care, natural language statements frequently conceal implicit assumptions, under-specify critical behaviours, or introduce unintended vagueness that becomes apparent only during system testing or operation. Such ambiguities are not merely stylistic defects: when left unresolved, they propagate throughout the development process, influencing architectural decisions, implementation strategies, and verification activities. More critically, requirements that are not grounded in a precise mathematical notation cannot benefit from the guarantees provided by formal verification techniques, which are essential for demonstrating compliance with rigorous industrial and regulatory standards for safety-critical software systems^{1,2,3}. These standards increasingly demand evidence that system behaviour has been analysed exhaustively and that potential faults—especially those arising from concurrency, non-determinism, or intricate reactive control—have been eliminated before deployment. However, bridging this gap between natural language and formal verification remains a substantial challenge in practice.

Creating formal specifications e.g.⁴ is a technically demanding task, requiring a solid foundation in formal logic, specification languages, and reasoning techniques. Engineers must not only understand the domain but also possess the specialised training needed to express requirements in a mathematically rigorous form and to manipulate these expressions through proof obligations, model-checking artefacts, or refinement steps. As a consequence, introducing formal specifications into an existing development workflow can significantly increase the effort and time required; empirical observations suggest that the specification and verification phases may lengthen the development cycle by roughly thirty percent⁵. For many organisations, operating under tight commercial timelines, the use of formal methods is compromised. We seek to mitigate the burden of writing formal specifications, enabling practitioners to reap the advantages of formal verification without requiring deep expertise in advanced proof methods or accepting prohibitive overheads. By doing so, we aim to narrow the long-standing gap between the theoretical value of formal verification and its limited adoption in mainstream software engineering practice.

The importance of accessible and effective formalisation becomes particularly clear when examining real-world systems in which subtle concurrency or coordination errors can have catastrophic consequences. Formalising requirements ensures not only clarity and internal consistency but also the ability to subject system behaviour to algorithmic scrutiny using techniques such as theorem proving and model checking. A compelling demonstration of this appears in the foundational work of⁶, which apply model checking to the plan execution module of NASA’s Remote Agent, flown on the Deep Space 1 mission. By translating ESL—a domain-specific reactive control language implemented in multi-threaded Common Lisp—into the PROMELA modelling language used by the SPIN model checker, the authors uncovered five previously undetected concurrency defects. Remarkably, one of these defects corresponded directly to a bug that later manifested as an in-flight deadlock, demonstrating that even extensive testing campaigns can fail to reveal elusive design flaws that formal analysis exposes with precision. As highlighted poignantly in⁶: “In fact, in a different part of the system, a concurrency bug identical to one discovered by this study escaped testing and caused a deadlock during an in-flight experiment 96 million kilometers from Earth.” This incident not only reaffirms the indispensable role of formal verification tools in safety-critical contexts but also stimulated the evolution of SPIN itself, inspiring the introduction of procedural abstraction through inline procedures to better support complex system modelling. Together, these observations illustrate both the necessity and the challenge of integrating formalism into requirements engineering. On one hand, formal methods demonstrably enhance system correctness, resilience, and predictability; on the other, their steep learning curve and labour-intensive nature impede widespread adoption. Like all other fields, the development of Large Language Models (LLMs) has opened a world of opportunities where we can exploit their power to generate formal requirements and accompanying specifications. This work aims to provide a feasibility to make the process of writing formal specifications more intuitive, less time-consuming, and more compatible with modern industrial development practices.

Generating Assertions

Adding annotations in imperative languages such as C, Java, and Dafny makes the intended behaviour of functions and contracts explicit, providing a precise semantic basis for verification tools. These annotations allow formal verifiers to reason about state changes and invariants, turning implicit programmer intent into machine-checkable correctness guarantees. Dafny is a verification-aware programming language that has native support for expressing formal specifications and is equipped with a static program verifier to automatically verify implementations against specifications using deductive verification. We illustrate an example using a Dafny lemma as reported in⁷, where a helper assertion is needed in the verification process. Lemmas are used in Dafny to specify properties that may be used in the verification process. The lemma, defined below, ensures that the integer and fractional parts are correctly extracted while parsing a decimal string.

The figure 1 presents the formal specification of the ParseDigitsAndDot lemma across three different languages and specification tools: Dafny, JML, and ACSL. Subfigure (a) illustrates the Dafny version of the lemma, which uses preconditions and postconditions to specify the correct behavior of string parsing, along with helper assertions in both the base and recursive cases. Subfigure (b) shows the JML annotations within a Java implementation, where similar preconditions and postconditions are defined, ensuring the string parsing behaves as expected. Finally, subfigure (c) demonstrates the equivalent ACSL annotations within C code, specifying the same formal properties and using assertions to validate the base and recursive cases.

Now, we explain the lemma body presented in Figure 1: The function’s **precondition** (the **requires** clause) states that every character in `s1` must be a digit ranging from ‘0’ to ‘9’. Its **postcondition** (the **ensures** clause) guarantees that when `ParseDecStr` is applied to the concatenation of `s1` and `s2`, the resulting pair preserves `s1` as the integer part while placing “.” + `s2` as the fractional part. In the **base case**, where `s1` consists of only one character, the function asserts that parsing “.” + `s2` yields an empty integer part. In the **recursive case**, the function processes the tail of `s1` by recursively calling

(b) JML Annotations with Java Code**(a) Dafny Lemma**

```

lemma ParseDigitsAndDot(s1: string, s2: string)
  requires forall i | 0 <= i < |s1|
    :: '0' <= s1[i] <= '9'
  ensures ParseDecStr(s1 + "." + s2).value.1
    == "." + s2
{
  if |s1| == 1 {
    assert ParseDecStr("." + s2).None?;
  } else {
    ParseDigitsAndDot(s1[1..], s2);
    assert s1 + "." + s2 ==
      [s1[0]] + (s1[1..] + "." + s2);
  }
}

```

```

/*@ requires (\forall int i;
  0 <= i && i < s1.length() ==>
  ('0' <= s1.charAt(i)
  &&
  s1.charAt(i) <= '9'));
  @ ensures ParseDecStr(s1 + "." + s2)
    .value[1].equals("." + s2);
  @*/
void ParseDigitsAndDot(String s1, String s2) {
  if (s1.length() == 1) {
    //@ assert ParseDecStr("." + s2).isNone();
  } else {
    ParseDigitsAndDot(s1.substring(1), s2);
    //@ assert (s1 + "." + s2).equals(
    //@   s1.charAt(0) + "" + (s1.substring(1)
    + "." + s2));
  }
}

```

(c) ACSL Annotations with C Code

```

/*@ requires \forall integer i;
  0 <= i < strlen(s1) ==>
  ('0' <= s1[i] && s1[i] <= '9');
  ensures ParseDecStr(concat3(s1, ".", s2)).value_1 ==
    concat(".", s2);
*/
void ParseDigitsAndDot(char* s1, char* s2) {
  if (strlen(s1) == 1) {
    //@ assert ParseDecStr(concat(".", s2)).None;
  } else {
    ParseDigitsAndDot(s1 + 1, s2);
    //@ assert concat3(s1, ".", s2) ==
    //@   concat3(char_to_string(s1[0]),
    //@   s1+1, concat(".", s2));
  }
}

```

FIGURE 1 (a) Dafny lemma, (b) JML annotations with Java code, and (c) ACSL annotations with C code for the 'ParseDigitsAndDot' lemma.

itself. To make the intended string decomposition clear to the verifier, an assertion is added: `assert s1 + "." + s2 == [s1[0]] + (s1[1..] + "." + s2);`. This assertion explicitly demonstrates how the string is broken down, which helps the SMT solver reason about the transformation and verify correctness.

Role of the Helper Assertion:

Without the assertion, the Dafny verifier struggles to establish the correctness of the postcondition due to the complexity of reasoning about string concatenation. The assertion serves as an intermediate step, breaking down the transformation into a form that is easier for the solver to handle.

This example motivates our work by demonstrating the importance of inserting specifications in the form of helper assertions in formal proofs using different specification languages. Tools like Laurel⁷ aim to automate this process by leveraging Large Language Models to determine the relevant assertions.

Key Contributions

This paper makes the following key contributions to the field of automated formal specification and software verification:

1. **Comprehensive Survey of AI-driven Formalisation:** We present an extensive review of more than one hundred recent research studies on translating natural language requirements into formal specifications. The survey highlights state-of-the-art methodologies, including natural language processing (NLP), ontology-based domain modelling, software artefact reuse, and the application of large language models (LLMs), providing a structured overview of effective approaches across programming languages and verification tools.

2. **Empirical Evaluation of Verification Tools:** The study performs a detailed empirical assessment of Frama-C plugins (RTE and EVA analysers) and the PathCrawler test generation tool. Experiments evaluate their capability to infer assertions, generate ACSL specifications, detect runtime errors, and explore execution paths in representative C programs. The results offer practical insights into tool strengths, limitations, and areas requiring human-guided intervention.
3. **Identification of Practical Challenges:** Through both survey and experiments, we highlight key barriers in automated formalisation, including solver instability, limited path coverage, ambiguous postconditions, and tool-specific constraints. This analysis informs strategies such as dataset adaptation, selective path exploration, and configuration tuning to enhance verification reliability.
4. **Roadmap for Intelligent Specification Workflows:** Based on observed results, we propose future directions for improving automation, traceability, and verifiability in high-assurance systems. This includes stronger solver support, richer ACSL templates, cross-tool orchestration, and human-in-the-loop strategies to achieve reliable and scalable formalisation.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 surveys existing research and synthesises key observations. This section contains several subsections that review major research directions, including LLM prompting strategies for program analysis, deductive-verification tooling, static-analysis frameworks, test-generation tools, and automated ACSL specification generation. Each subsection outlines core contributions, methodological trends, and gaps in the current state of the art. Section 3 then describes our methodology for running initial experiments with PathCrawler, using prompts adapted from⁸. Here, sub-section 3.2 presents the empirical evaluation of deductive verifiers on the 36-program Frama-C tutorial set. Following this, sub-section 4.1 reports the results of static analysis performed with EVA on the dataset provided by⁸, after which ACSL annotations generated by RTE are evaluated with deductive verifiers. Experience with Pathcrawler test case generation is reported in sub-section 4.3.

Section 5 synthesises insights from both the literature and empirical evaluations to outline the major challenges and corresponding future research directions. Each subsection discusses a specific challenge—such as variability in LLM-generated prompts, limitations in ACSL specification quality, interoperability issues across verification tools, scalability constraints when analysing larger programs, insufficient standardised benchmarks, and the need for more rigorous evaluators—and pairs it with actionable future directions aligned with these findings. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper by summarising contributions and outlining possible avenues for extending automated verification workflows.

2 | STATE OF THE ART

This section reviews prior work that forms the basis for our investigation into automated software verification and specification generation. The goal is to situate our methodology and experimental design within the broader context of existing tools, analysis techniques, and recent attempts to incorporate large language models into verification workflows. We survey contributions spanning deductive verification, static analysis, automated test generation, and ACSL specification inference, with particular attention to empirical findings and methodological practices reported in the literature. By examining these developments together, we identify the recurring patterns, assumptions, and limitations that shape current approaches. The synthesis provided here serves as the foundation for the experimental choices and evaluation criteria used in the remainder of the paper.

2.1 | Methodology for Literature Review

In this section, we present the results of our structured literature review which examines how large language models are currently used to assist in writing formal specifications. Main research questions for conducting systematic literature review on the topic are as follows:

RQ1: What methodologies leverage Large Language Models (LLMs) to transform natural language software requirements into formal notations?

RQ2: What are the emerging trends and future research directions in using LLMs for software requirements formalisation?

To conduct a structured and thorough review of literature on Natural Language Processing (NLP), Large Language Models (LLMs), and their use in software requirements, the following approach is followed. Several academic databases, including IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, Scopus, Springer Link, and Google Scholar, are searched using specific keywords. The core search terms include “NLP,” “LLMs,” and “Software Requirements,” with broader terms such as “specification,” “logic,” “verification,” “model checking,” and “theorem proving” used to expand the scope. The number of results differs notably across

databases, with some sources returning only small collections of studies, while Google Scholar provides large volume of 8,640 references. It reduced to 7,780 when filter of since 2021 is applied. These discrepancies highlight the importance of applying precise selection methods to extract the most relevant studies.

To streamline the process of locating strong contributions, the AI-powered tool Elicit⁹ is used. Elicit supports the literature review by offering summarised content and DOIs for suggested papers. While it helps reduce the manual workload during the initial phase, every suggested paper in this review is manually reviewed to ensure its relevance. This ensures that the final list excludes any unrelated or off-topic material. After the initial filtering, a manual review is performed to confirm the relevance and quality of each paper. Abstracts are first assessed to judge suitability. If the abstract lacks clarity or depth, a further examination of the full text is conducted.

Abstracts are closely read, and when necessary, the full text is reviewed using the following exclusion and inclusion criteria:

Inclusion Criteria: Studies are included if they offer meaningful theoretical or empirical insights related to NLP, LLMs, and their application in software requirements. This includes topics like specification, formal logic, verification, and formal methods.

Exclusion Criteria: Papers are excluded if they show in-sufficient relevance to the intersection of NLP/LLMs and software requirements, or if their abstracts or full texts lack sufficient detail. Non-peer-reviewed materials, duplicates, and items suggested by Elicit but deemed irrelevant after manual review are also removed.

Figure 2 represents a tree-like structure of the literature review related to LLM-Based Specification and Verification.

FIGURE 2 LLM-Based Verification and Specification Literature Overview

2.2 | Formalising Requirements through LLMs

This section provides an integrated overview of the literature surveyed, supported by a set of structured tables that summarise and categorise the body of work examined. Table 5 organises the surveyed papers according to the methodological lens through which they approach specification generation, verification, and tool-assisted reasoning, enabling readers to quickly identify clusters of research such as prompt-only approaches, verifier-in-the-loop workflows, fine-tuned models, neuro-symbolic pipelines, and dataset-driven contributions. A more detailed breakdown is provided in Table 6, which extends the classification by including for each reference the specific tool, framework, or technique under consideration as well as a concise summary of its contribution, evaluation method, and reported outcomes. This granular presentation illustrates how diverse approaches—from NL-to-LTL translation and class-invariant inference to dataset construction and IDE-integrated verification

assistance—contribute to the broader landscape of automation in software verification. Later, we used the iterative approach to extend the state-of-the-art, while conducting our experiments. Table 7 compiles the most recent and state-of-the-art developments, offering extended descriptions of works that combine LLM-based inference with symbolic reasoning, retrieval-augmented pipelines, benchmark creation, interactive proof systems, agentic frameworks, and domain-specific verification.

2.2.1 | LLM-Assisted Verification and Specification Tools

PALM is introduced in¹⁰, which is a generate-then-repair framework that combines large language models with symbolic reasoning to improve formal proof generation in Coq. Through analysis of 520 proof generation errors made by GPT-3.5, Minghai et al. identify that LLMs often capture the high-level proof structure but fail in low-level details, motivating PALM’s iterative repair mechanism. Evaluated on a dataset of over 10,000 theorems, PALM achieves 76.6%-180.4% higher success rates and proves 1,270 additional theorems beyond existing methods, demonstrating strong performance and generalizability across multiple LLMs. The paper¹¹ introduces AutoSpec, an automated framework for synthesizing formal specifications that enables end-to-end program verification without extensive manual effort. It extends beyond prior approaches that are limited to narrow domains, supporting complex program structures involving arrays, pointers, nested loops, and function calls. AutoSpec combines static analysis and program verification in an iterative synthesis loop that incrementally refines and validates candidate specifications, ensuring satisfiability and proof adequacy throughout the process. Empirical evaluation demonstrates its strong performance, successfully verifying 79% of benchmark programs—a 1.592x improvement over existing methods—and further confirming its applicability through verification of the real-world X509-parser project.

The paper¹² proposes using LLMs, like GPT-3.5, to verify code by analysing requirements and explaining whether they are met. The work¹³ provides verification and refinement of natural language explanations by making LLMs and theorem provers work together. A neuro-symbolic framework i.e. Explanation-Refiner is represented. LLMs and theorem provers are integrated together to formalise explanatory sentences. The theorem prover then provides the guarantee of validated sentence explanations. Theorem prover also provides feedback for further improvements in NLI (Natural Language Inference) model. Error correction mechanisms can also be deployed by using the tool Explanation-Refiner. Consequently, it automatically enhances the quality of explanations of variable complexity.

The work¹⁴ evaluated GPT-4o’s ability to generate specifications for C programs that can be verified using VeriFast, a static verifier based on separation logic. Their experiments, which use different user inputs and prompting techniques, show that while GPT-4o’s specifications maintain functional behaviour, they often fail verification and include redundancies when verifiable. The paper¹⁵ introduced OntoChat, a conversational agent that integrates large language models to assist users throughout the Ontology Requirements Engineering (ORE) process. It addresses the limitations of traditional, manual ORE methods by exploring how LLMs can automate and enhance tasks such as requirements elicitation, documentation, and validation.¹⁵ presented preliminary findings from the first year of research, demonstrating the potential of LLM-driven interaction to make ontology engineering more efficient, consistent, and collaborative.

The paper¹⁶ presents HILBERT, an integrated agentic framework that unites informal mathematical reasoning with formal verification to advance automated theorem proving. The system coordinates four synergistic components—an informal reasoning model for high-level mathematical insight, a Lean 4-optimized prover, a formal verifier, and a semantic theorem retriever—to collaboratively construct, verify, and refine formal proofs. When the prover encounters unsolved problems, HILBERT applies recursive decomposition to partition them into smaller subgoals, which are then resolved using either the prover or the informal reasoning agent. The framework incorporates verifier-guided feedback loops to iteratively correct and strengthen incomplete or erroneous proofs, ensuring semantic consistency across the reasoning process. Experimental evaluation demonstrates that HILBERT achieves state-of-the-art performance, with 99.2% accuracy on miniF2F—surpassing the best existing method by 6.6 percentage points—and solving 462 out of 660 problems (70.0%) on PutnamBench, outperforming proprietary systems such as SeedProver (50.4%) and achieving a 422% improvement over the best publicly available baseline. Collectively, these results establish HILBERT as a major step forward in bridging the divide between informal mathematical reasoning and fully verified formal proof synthesis.

2.2.2 | Frameworks for Specification Synthesis

The work¹⁷ details about nl2spec, a framework that leverages LLMs to generate formal specifications from natural language, addressing the challenge of ambiguity in system requirements. Users can iteratively refine translations, making formalization

easier. The work¹⁷ provides an open-source implementation with a web-based interface. An automatic synthesis of software specifications is provided through LLMs in¹⁸. Work¹⁸ proposed SpecSyn framework that uses an advanced language model to automatically generate software specifications from natural language text. It treats specification generation as a sequence-to-sequence learning task and outperforms previous tools by 21% in accuracy, extracting specifications from both single and multiple sentences.

The paper¹⁹ introduces LEMUR, a rigorous framework that integrates automated reasoning with structured synthesis to improve loop invariant generation and program verification. Unlike prior learning-based approaches such as Code2Inv, which rely solely on reinforcement learning, LEMUR establishes a formal calculus that unifies symbolic reasoning and guided invariant inference under a provably sound framework. Evaluated on the Code2Inv benchmark set of 133 C programs, LEMUR employs the ESBMC k-induction verifier to validate synthesized invariants and significantly outperforms both ESBMC alone and Code2Inv. Specifically, LEMUR(GPT-4) solves 107 benchmarks within a 10-minute timeout, compared to only 68 by ESBMC and fewer by Code2Inv under a longer one-hour limit. The framework’s adaptive generation strategy allows it to converge to correct invariants typically within four iterations, though complex cases may require more. Moreover, comparative evaluation with LEMUR(GPT-3.5) reveals that stronger symbolic reasoning oracles lead to both faster convergence and higher verification success rates, highlighting the importance of well-structured reasoning integration rather than heuristic generation.

Extending the evaluation to the SV-COMP 2023 benchmark suite,¹⁹ demonstrates LEMUR’s robustness on challenging verification tasks that traditional tools cannot resolve. On 47 benchmarks unsolved by ESBMC and UAutomizer, LEMUR(GPT-4) successfully verifies 25 instances, including programs with multiple nested loops, achieving dramatic performance gains where baseline verifiers each solved only one. The results reveal LEMUR’s ability to infer non-trivial invariants—such as modular arithmetic relationships and disjunctive conditions—not explicitly represented in source code, surpassing the expressiveness of predicate-abstraction-based techniques. The framework’s iterative refinement mechanism, guided by verifier feedback, ensures that candidate invariants remain both semantically sound and provably sufficient. Beyond empirical achievements, the paper outlines a clear path for future research, including specialization to back-end verifiers, adaptation to functional languages, and development of domain-specific prompting languages for complex logical formula synthesis. Together, these contributions establish LEMUR as a comprehensive and extensible foundation for formal verification through structured invariant synthesis, setting new standards in precision, scalability, and theoretical grounding for automated reasoning frameworks.

The paper²⁰ introduced Req2Spec, an NLP-based tool that analyses natural language requirements to create formal specifications for HANFOR”, a large-scale requirements and test generation tool. Tested on 222 automotive software requirements at BOSCH, it correctly formalized 71% of them. The work²¹ represents a novel framework named SpecGen to generate specifications through LLMs. Two phases are applied. First phase is about having prompts in conversational style. Second phase is deployed where correct specifications are not generated. Here, four mutation operators are applied to ensure the correctness of the generated specifications. Two benchmarks i.e. SV-COMP and SpecGen are used. Verifiable specifications are generated successfully for 279 out of 384 programs, making²¹ a viable approach.

The paper²² introduces RvLLM, a runtime verification framework that leverages domain-specific knowledge encoded in a custom specification language (ESL) to systematically detect and correct erroneous outputs. RvLLM operates in a two-stage process of interpretation and reasoning, where context-driven interpretations guide the identification of inconsistencies, and iterative follow-up queries ensure output consistency. The framework was evaluated on three representative tasks—violation detection against the Singapore Rapid Transit Systems Act, numerical comparison, and inequality solving—across multiple LLMs including Qwen (max, plus, turbo, 2.5 variants), GPT-4.1 (mini, nano), Gemini 2.0 Flash (Lite), and DeepSeek-V3²². In violation detection, RvLLM improved true positive rates substantially, for instance raising Qwen max from 56.2% to 86.1% and GPT-4.1 from 57.7% to 81.1%, while maintaining or slightly adjusting true negative rates. On numerical comparison tasks, LLMs guided by RvLLM consistently produced correct and inconclusive results, with Qwen 2.5 (32B) achieving 98 correct and 2 inconclusive outputs within 4.98 seconds, demonstrating considerable gains over baseline performance. In inequality solving involving factorization, interval analysis, and endpoint checking, RvLLM enabled higher true positive rates, reaching 50% for Qwen 2.5 (32B) on factorization tasks, showcasing its ability to enforce domain-specific constraints effectively.

²³ presents SpecVerify, a framework that integrates large language models with formal verification tools to automatically derive and verify properties from natural language requirements. By combining Claude 3.5 Sonnet with the ESBMC verifier, it achieves verification accuracy comparable to NASA’s CoCoSim while reducing false positives and extending assertion expressiveness beyond traditional logics. The paper²⁴ presents a structured approach for automatically synthesizing runtime verification monitors directly from natural language specifications. The method operates in staged transformations—first translating informal requirements into propositional past-time LTL formulas, and then generating corresponding runtime monitors

based on these formal representations. The process incorporates self-validation steps within each synthesis stage, allowing the system to iteratively refine outputs and substantially improve the correctness of the generated monitors. The paper²⁵ investigates an integrated approach for automatically discovering inductive loop invariants, a long-standing challenge in formal verification. Using a curated benchmark comprising 1,025 C programs with diverse loop structures, the study evaluates GPT-4, GPT-3.5, and Code Llama in conjunction with Frama-C's WP tool and SMT solvers to assess the soundness of generated invariants. The proposed method combines symbolic reasoning with data-driven synthesis, where candidate invariants are generated and formally validated through automated proof obligations.

2.2.3 | Domain-Specific and Security-Focused Applications

AssertLLM tool is presented in²⁶. The tool generates assertions to do hardware verification from design specifications, exploiting three customised LLMs. It is done in three phases, first understanding specifications, mapping signal definitions and generating assertions. The results show that AssertLLM produced 89% correct assertions with accurate syntax and function. The work²⁷ reports on formal verification of NASA's Node Control Software natural language specifications. The software is deployed at International Space Station. Errors found in the natural language requirements are reported by the authors with a commentary on lessons learnt.

SpecLLM²⁸ explores the space of generating and reviewing VLSI design specifications with LLMs. The utility of LLMs is explored with the two stages i.e. (1) **generation** of architecture specifications from scratch and from register transfer logic (RTL) code; and (2) **reviewing** these generated specifications. In²⁹, the potential and power of LLMs is exploited for smart grid requirement specifications improvement. Here, the performance of GPT-4o and Claude 3.5 Sonnet is analysed through f1-scores, achieving in range of 79% - 94%.

The research presented in³⁰ introduces SV-LLM, a multi-agent large language model system purpose-built for automating security verification of complex system-on-chip (SoC) designs. The framework integrates domain-specialized agents that coordinate tasks such as security asset identification, threat modeling, property generation, vulnerability detection, and simulation-based bug validation. Each agent operates using distinct learning paradigms—fine-tuning, in-context learning, and retrieval-augmented generation—to generate precise, verifiable security specifications from design data and documentation. This agentic architecture directly targets SoC-level verification challenges by embedding reasoning capabilities tailored to register-transfer-level (RTL) semantics and design constraints.

Experimental evaluations in³⁰ demonstrate substantial gains in RTL security analysis accuracy and efficiency. The fine-tuned Security Vulnerability Detection Agent, based on Mistral-7B-Instruct, achieves 84.8% accuracy—an improvement of 42.3 percentage points over its non-fine-tuned baseline—while remaining transparent and resource-efficient compared to closed-source models. The Bug Validation Agent attains up to 89% validated testbench generation across diverse RTL designs, outperforming zero-shot prompting methods by more than fourfold. These results confirm that³⁰ delivers a practical and high-performing framework for scalable, explainable, and domain-adapted SoC security verification.

2.2.4 | Safety-Critical and Prover-Integrated Applications

The work³¹ introduced LeanDojo, an open-source toolkit that enables programmatic interaction with Lean theorem prover. Using LeanDojo's extracted data,³¹ developed ReProver, a retrieval-augmented LLM-based prover. Thor³² is a framework developed to integrate language models with theorem provers. It improved the accuracy from 39% to 57% using the PISA dataset and also outperformed previous works on the MiniF2F dataset. The paper³³ explores integrating Co-pilot with formal methods. The integration of Copilot and formal methods is proposed through development of IDE containing language servers. Granberry et al.⁸ explored combining LLMs with symbolic analysis to generate specifications for C programs. They enhanced LLM prompts using outputs from PathCrawler and EVA to produce ACSL annotations.

³⁴ investigates the feasibility of applying formal software verification to LLM-generated code using the SPARK framework for Ada.³⁴ introduced Marmaragan, a tool that employs an LLM to automatically generate SPARK annotations for existing programs, thereby enabling their formal verification. Evaluated on a curated SPARK benchmark with selectively removed annotations, Marmaragan powered by GPT-4o achieves 50.7% correctness in annotation generation. The study³⁵ explores the use of Generative AI for the automatic synthesis of code contracts—specifically pre- and postconditions—for Java programs without relying on any auxiliary artifacts. The authors fine-tuned CodeT5 and CodeT5+ models on a newly curated dataset of over 14,000

Java methods annotated with Java Modeling Language (JML) specifications, enabling the models to learn precise contract generation. Their evaluation on unseen software projects demonstrated that over 95% of the generated contracts were syntactically valid and exhibited strong semantic accuracy and completeness, underscoring the potential of LLMs to advance automated software verification and Design-by-Contract methodologies. The work by³⁶ presents a compiler that translates higher-order logic meaning representations, derived from Java method-level comments, into formal Java Modeling Language (JML) specifications. This translation bridges natural-language-based semantic representations and formal verification by resolving predicate ambiguities and aligning them with first-order logic constructs. Evaluation on Java API benchmarks demonstrates high accuracy, with 94% correct JML generation and 97% of those verifiable using an automated theorem prover.

In³⁷, symbolic NLP and ChatGPT performance is compared while generating correct formal contracts written in the Java Modelling Language (JML) which have been extracted from natural language specifications. The paper³⁸ reports the translation between NL and Linear Temporal Logic (LTL) formulas through the use of LLMs. Dynamic prompt generation and human interaction with LLMs are amalgamated to deal with the mentioned challenges. Unstructured natural language requirements are converted to NL-LTL pairs. The approach achieved up to 94.4% accuracy on publicly available datasets with 36 and 255,000 NL-LTL pairs. The primitive work³⁹ described automatic translation from natural language sentences to temporal logic, in order to deploy formal verification of the requirements.

2.2.5 | Hybrid Symbolic-LLM Methodologies

SAT-LLM, a unique framework to remove conflicting requirements is represented in⁴⁰. It integrated Satisfiability Modulo Theories (SMT) solvers with LLMs. SAT-LLM performed better than ChatGPT alone, identifying 80% of conflicts with a Precision of 1.00, Recall of 0.83, and an F1 score of 0.91.⁴¹ outlines key research directions for the stages of software requirement engineering, conducts a SWOT analysis, and share findings from an initial evaluation.

The purpose of Dafny is to automate proofs by outsourcing them to an SMT solver.⁷ presented a framework named Laurel to generate Dafny assertions using LLMs. Laurel was able to generate over 50% of the required helper assertions.⁴² used input of error messages, variable names, procedure documentation and user questions. They discussed available literature for generating assertions by synthesising sentences in testing phase. Reporting about DafnyBench⁴³, Chloe et al. evaluated the capability of GPT-4 and Claude 3 to automatically generate sufficient hints, enabling the Dafny formal verification engine to successfully verify over 750 programs comprising approximately 53,000 lines of code. The most effective combination of model and prompting strategy achieved a 68% verification success rate, with further analysis showing that this rate improves through iterative retries using error feedback but declines as program size and hint complexity increase.

The paper⁴⁴ introduced a model-based language (Requirements Specification Language - RSL). The framework functionality is integrated as development platform named ReDSeeDS. A similar work is reported in⁴⁵ which describes the ARSENAL framework and methodology designed to perform automatic requirements specification extraction from natural language. An interesting work is presented in⁴⁶. It includes generation of natural language from business process models. The generated natural language is found complete and more understandable. In primitive work of 1996⁴⁷, software requirements were expressed in a limited set of natural language referred to as controlled natural language. The primitive work in the domain is about RML⁴⁸. RML bundled with features of writing requirements, which are based on conceptual model.

2.2.6 | Advanced Prompt Engineering

In this sub-section, we outline prospective directions informed by the literature review. Much of the literature in this review employed queries containing a problem description and some instructions to achieve a desired outcome. Such querying of LLMs without training or examples of the current task is typically referred as zero-shot prompting and shows excellent performance on many tasks⁴⁹. Surprisingly, they also showed that the performance of LLM on some challenging problems can be improved by encouraging the LLM to reason using intermediate steps through a simple addition to problem prompts (Lets think step by step).

Beyond this approach is one-shot prompting that includes an example of a solved problem to guide the LLM into generating the desired output⁵⁰. This can be extended to few-shot prompting where a number of differing examples guide the LLM. But improved results are not assured as some studies e.g.⁵¹ show that zero-shot can outperform the few-shot case⁵².⁵³ reviewed the evolution of prompt engineering in LLMs, including discussions on self-consistency and multimodal prompt learning. It also reviewed the literature related to adversarial attacks and evaluation strategies for ensuring robust AI interactions.

Chain of Thought (CoT)⁵⁴ prompting involves a sequence of prompts producing intermediate results that are generated by the LLM and used to drive subsequent prompting interactions. These orchestrated interactions can improve LLM performance on tasks requiring logic, calculation and decision-making in areas like math, common sense reasoning, and symbolic manipulation. CoT requires the LLM to articulate the distinct steps of its reasoning, by subdividing larger tasks into multi-step reasoning stages, acting as a precursor for subsequent stages. But the CoT approach may require careful analysis when used with larger LLM offering long input contexts. This is because of the lost-in-the-middle problem where LLM show a U-shaped attention bias⁵³ and can fail to attend to information in the middle of the context window.

PromptCoT⁵⁵ enhanced the quality of solutions for diffusion-based generative models by employing the CoT approach. The computational cost is minimised through adapter-based fine-tuning. Prompt design is explored in detail in⁵⁶. It discussed Chain-of-Thought and Reflection techniques, along with best practices for structuring prompts and building LLM-based agents.

Besta et al.⁵⁷ introduced the concept of reasoning topologies, examining how structures such as Chains, Trees, and Graphs of Thought improve LLM reasoning. They also proposed a taxonomy of structured reasoning techniques, highlighting their influence on both performance and efficiency. Structured Chain-of-Thought (SCoT) prompting was proposed by⁵⁸ to enhance code generation by incorporating structured programming principles. This approach significantly improved the accuracy and robustness of LLM-based code synthesis compared to standard CoT methods. Building on the theme of automation,⁵⁹ introduced Automate-CoT, a technique for automatically generating and selecting rational chains for CoT prompting. By minimising dependence on human annotations, it enabled more flexible adaptation of CoT strategies across diverse reasoning tasks. Complementing these efforts,⁶⁰ presented a prompt pattern catalog that offered reusable design patterns to optimise LLM interactions, thereby refining prompt engineering practices for a wide range of applications. Additionally,⁶¹ proposed Reprompting (Gibbs sampling-based algorithm) for discovering optimal CoT prompts. The proposed prompting technique consistently outperformed human-crafted alternatives and demonstrated high adaptability across various reasoning benchmarks.

Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG)⁶² supplements problem information with specifically retrieved information and is often used in knowledge intensive tasks. This helps ensure the LLM attends specifically to the retrieved information when addressing the users prompt. LLM model selection (chat vs reasoning) and fine tuning such as with LoRA⁶³ remain among a growing number of possibilities for exploration.

2.2.7 | Evaluation of LLM-Assisted Specification and Verification Literature

Explanation-Refiner integrates LLMs with theorem provers for NLI validation and iterative correction¹³. Evaluation of GPT-4o with VeriFast shows generation of functional specifications, though verification remains limited due to redundancy and failed assertions¹⁴.

The nl2spec tool supports interactive synthesis from unstructured requirements¹⁷, while the SpecSyn tool improves sequence-to-sequence contract generation with a 21% accuracy gain¹⁸. Req2Spec converts 71% of BOSCH automotive requirements into formal specs²⁰, while SpecGen uses prompt mutation and verification feedback to improve LLM-generated specifications, succeeding on 279 out of 384 benchmark programs²¹. In the hardware domain, AssertLLM synthesizes assertions with 89% correctness via multi-phase prompting and validation²⁶, while VLSI applications leverage LLMs for spec review and generation in SpecLLM²⁸. Smart grid requirements have been formalised using GPT-4o and Claude 3.5, achieving F1 scores between 79% and 94%²⁹. The trend in F1-scores observed by authors of²⁹ suggested that GPT-4o and Claude 3.5 not only maintain robustness but may actually benefit from increased system specification complexity, highlighting a potential alignment between model reasoning depth and specification richness. This aspect not mirrored in Gemini 1.5 or GPT-3.5-turbo and warranting further investigation. NASA's software verification effort surfaced requirement errors, demonstrating practical utility of LLM-in-the-loop workflows²⁷.

NL-to-LTL translation has seen progress via few-shot prompting and dynamic reasoning³⁸, achieving 94.4% accuracy. Likewise, NL-to-JML contract synthesis for Java programs has been explored with promising results³⁷. Historical systems like RSL⁴⁴, ARSENAL⁴⁵, and RML⁴⁸ demonstrated early rule-based and logic-based extraction pipelines, while hybrid neuro-symbolic systems offer greater reliability. SAT-LLM couples SMT solvers with LLMs to detect inconsistencies with F1 of 0.91⁴⁰ and LeanDojo, ReProver, and Thor enhance formal proving via retrieval-augmented generation and LLM-guided reasoning^{31,32}. IDE-integrated efforts like those combining Copilot with PathCrawler and EVA demonstrate semi-automated ACSL specification generation^{33,8}.

As we expected, assertion-level synthesis shows better reliability than full contract generation. For example, Laurel generates assertions for Dafny with over 50% success⁷, and AssertLLM exceeds 89% correctness when guided by contract type and context. Full specifications are more error-prone, often requiring multiple prompt iterations or external validation²¹.

LLM selection and prompting strategies critically affect performance. While zero-shot prompting is strong in base performance⁴⁹, one-shot⁵⁰ and few-shot⁵² offer alternative trade-offs. Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting improves logical flow via intermediate steps⁵⁴, and like Structured CoT (SCoT)⁵⁸ it can suffer from context decay in long prompts (lost-in-the-middle)⁵³, yet zero-shot often remains competitive⁵¹.

Advanced prompting methods like Automate-CoT generate CoT examples automatically⁵⁹, while Reprompting uses Gibbs sampling to escape prompt local optima⁶¹. Structured prompting with graphs and trees improves reasoning robustness and efficiency⁵⁷. RAG (Retrieval-Augmented Generation) improves grounding for knowledge-intensive synthesis⁶².⁶⁴ discusses a wider range of almost 30 prompting strategies, some of which seem not to have been explored in relation to formalising specifications. Of course, this does not include related approaches such as fine-tuning LLM via LoRA adaptation training⁶³, but this may only be applicable when there is access to the LLM's architecture and weights. Additionally, reinforcement learning (RL) may help with specific challenges, opening even more avenues for exploration.

We observed a significant difference between the success rates of assertion generation and full contract synthesis using LLMs. AssertLLM²⁶ and Laurel⁷ achieved high accuracy in generating helper assertions for programs written in Dafny language⁶⁵ and design-specific verification statements. These tools achieved an accuracy of 89% and over 50%, operating at a local level on source code or isolated signals. On the other hand,³⁷ reported that while generating formal specifications for Java Modelling Language (JML) contracts or temporal logic formulas ended up in frequent verification failures by the SMT solvers embedded in OpenJML⁶⁶. This happened even if the output appeared semantically sound, leading to the conclusion of disparity between human-readable correctness and automated formal verification, especially when the source code was written for complex tasks.

In general, we observed that tasks with small scope and well-defined semantics yield better results where the limited context in these assertions helps in improving verification accuracy^{21,18}. LLMs handle such tasks more reliably due to reduced ambiguity and fewer dependencies on broader system knowledge. On the other hand, for larger program segments, end-to-end contract synthesis involves multiple interacting components or function bodies. It demands a deeper understanding of program semantics, logic, and behaviour over time. SpecGen²¹ and SpecSyn¹⁸ presented significant progress in tackling such challenges. However, their outputs require post-processing steps, such as mutation operators or human-in-the-loop (software testing experts were involved), before the generated outputs are usable for formal verification.

The effort accuracy is influenced by tool design and integration. For example, tools like n12spec¹⁷ improve generated specification quality through step-by-step refinement, adopting iterative and user-in-the-loop approach to help address some LLM limitations. Similarly, prompt engineering techniques utilising guided templates or Chain-of-Thought (CoT)^{14,67,55} promised improved output coherence and correctness. These strategies work well in scenarios involving localised tasks, such as assertion synthesis or narrow-scope descriptions. As the program size and complexity of the specification goal increase, the chances of ambiguity, under-specification, and logical inconsistency increase. Therefore, we conclude that the current LLM architectures excel in focused, declarative tasks but require augmentation for broader specification goals. However,⁶⁸ showed that different versions of language models including LLM, can vary greatly in their responses to the same queries, suggesting that much experimental work might be required to achieve optimum results.

We conclude from our synthesis of the current literature that the research trend is increasing in combining the strength of LLMs, symbolic reasoning and iterative user interaction. At the moment, assertion generation dominates in terms of accuracy and usability, but the parallel efforts of better prompt design, domain-specific fine-tuning, and verifier-in-the-loop are closely matching the performance of the process. The challenges of abstraction and consistency drive research efforts in this domain.

2.3 | Curated Benchmarking Datasets

The PURE dataset⁶⁹, comprising 34,268 sentences drawn from 79 software requirements documents, was employed to simulate realistic conditions under which natural language requirements are translated into formal specifications. This dataset facilitates the evaluation of large language models (LLMs) for their ability to produce ACSL-style annotations from informal textual descriptions, detect ambiguity and inconsistency in human-authored requirements, and synthesize specifications at the document level. A selected subset of PURE was used to prompt an LLM to generate ACSL specifications purely from textual input. These generated annotations were then validated against hand-written or automatically synthesized counterparts for consistency and correctness using the same Frama-C toolchain adopted in this empirical study. Complementary analysis was conducted using

the CLEVER dataset to benchmark cross-framework specification expressiveness⁷⁰. The CLEVER collection supports verified code generation in the Lean proof assistant and thus provides a point of comparison between high-assurance formal systems and C-based verification. This experiment investigates the relative completeness and precision of LLM-generated ACSL annotations compared with Lean specifications. It further explores translation heuristics between Lean-style and ACSL-style contract patterns. For this purpose, a representative subset of CLEVER tasks was adapted into behavior-preserving C function equivalents and analyzed within the Frama-C verification pipeline.

The paper⁷¹ introduces CORE, a human-verified benchmark that rigorously evaluates large language models on fundamental static analysis tasks involving data and control dependency, along with information flow across multiple programming languages. It further provides a semantics-aware diverse sampling strategy and comprehensive evaluation revealing that current LLMs excel at simple dependency detection but struggle with deep semantic reasoning and multi-step program understanding. The CrossCodeEval benchmark⁷² was utilized to examine how effectively specifications can be synthesized in the presence of cross-file and multi-language dependencies. This dataset incorporates code in multiple languages—including Python, Java, TypeScript, and C# and is designed to evaluate the influence of contextual information on specification accuracy. The experimental setup measures whether expanding LLM prompts with cross-file or cross-language context improves the completeness and fidelity of generated ACSL-style annotations. Static analysis was applied to extract relevant inter-file relationships, and synthesized specifications were validated either within their native ecosystems (e.g., Python with Pytype or MyPy) or translated into C for consistency checking under the Frama-C framework.

⁷³ introduced VerifyThisBench, a comprehensive benchmark that evaluates large language models on end-to-end program verification, encompassing natural language interpretation, formal specification, code generation, and proof construction. The study reveals that even state-of-the-art models like o3-mini achieve below 4% pass rates, highlighting significant challenges in formal reasoning and motivating the development of a simplified variant, VerifyThisBenchXS, to further analyze model capabilities. The proposed approach achieves a 12%-22% pass rate, marking a notable enhancement compared to the prior 4% performance.

⁷⁴ presented ClassInvGen, a method that co-generates executable class invariants and corresponding test inputs to improve the precision and reliability of inferred specifications for C++ programs. It demonstrates clear advantages over existing specification generation and invariant inference techniques, including Daikon, in both correctness and completeness of results. The authors also introduce a benchmark suite of standard C++ data structures and an accompanying evaluation harness for systematic testing and mutation-based validation of generated invariants. A case study on a high-integrity industrial C++ codebase further confirms the effectiveness and real-world applicability of the approach.

Verina⁷⁵ is a comprehensive benchmark, comprising 189 manually curated coding tasks in Lean, each accompanied by precise problem statements, reference implementations, formal specifications, and exhaustive test suites. Through an extensive evaluation of leading models, the study highlights persistent challenges in verifiable code generation, particularly in the domain of formal proof synthesis. The reported results underscore the current limitations of automated theorem proving, with the top-performing model, OpenAI o4-mini, attaining only 61.4% correctness in code, 51.0% in specification soundness and completeness, and a notably low 3.6% success rate in proof generation (based on single-trial evaluations).

⁷⁶ introduced C-ACSL (CASP), a curated evaluation set comprising 506 C functions paired with ACSL specifications, constructed through a multi-stage extraction and verification pipeline applied to two stacks of programs. The pipeline consists of three steps: Step 1 filters C files from The Stack v1 and v2 to identify those containing ACSL specifications without external dependencies; Step 2 compiles and verifies each annotated file, using LLM-based automatic repair and re-evaluation when verification fails; and Step 3 transforms all successfully verified files into minimal specificationimplementation pairs for inclusion in CASP. Only those ACSL-annotated C files are retained which are formally verified by Frama-C. Authors used LLM-based refinement to recover additional non-verifying candidates. Each surviving specificationimplementation pair is post-processed and manually validated, yielding a dataset of rigorously verified CACSL pairs.

2.4 | Requirements and Formal Verification Ecosystems

Ensuring correctness and traceability in safety-critical software requires specialized tools for requirements management, formalization, verification, and static analysis. IBM Engineering Requirements Management DOORS provides enterprise-grade

capabilities for capturing, linking, tracing, and analyzing requirements across regulated domains such as aerospace, automotive, and medical devices, supporting version control, collaboration, and compliance.[‡] FRET (Formal Requirements Elicitation Tool) from NASA Ames formalizes hierarchical requirements using the structured natural-language interface “FRETish,” translating them into formal logic, enabling visualization, simulation, and iterative verification to reduce ambiguity in safety-critical specifications.[§] FrameNet, maintained by ICSI Berkeley, provides a lexicographic resource mapping lexical units to semantic frames, facilitating natural-language processing, information extraction, and translation of human-readable requirements into machine-interpretable semantics.[¶] EARS (Easy Approach to Requirements Syntax) offers template-based patterns that improve readability, reduce ambiguity, and increase testability of natural-language requirements without heavy tooling, making it suitable for teams of all sizes.[#] Kapture enforces clarity, atomicity, and consistency in embedded and safety-critical system requirements, providing automated consistency checks and traceability to minimize review subjectivity.^{||} SonarQube supports static analysis for C/C++ and other languages, detecting code smells, vulnerabilities, and technical debt while integrating into DevOps pipelines and enabling “Quality Gates” to prevent noncompliant code from merging.^{**} Frama-C offers a modular framework for static analysis, formal verification, and certification of C programs in high-integrity systems, providing plug-ins for slicing, value analysis, weakest-precondition generation, and proof management to ensure runtime safety.^{††} Together, these tools facilitate rigorous requirement specification, semantic interpretation, and code verification, supporting safer and more reliable software development.

Frama-C was selected as the primary verification framework in this research due to its comprehensive, extensible, and research-driven ecosystem that has matured over nearly two decades of continuous academic and industrial development. Originating from collaborative efforts led by CEA List (France) and enriched through numerous European research initiatives, Frama-C stands as one of the most rigorously engineered environments for analyzing and verifying C programs used in safety-critical domains. Its modular architecture supports interoperability and specialization through an evolving set of over twenty-three plug-ins, enabling users to combine diverse formal methods within a unified interface. Notable among these are the Value Analysis, Eva, WP (Weakest Precondition), AstraVer, E-ACSL, RTE, Slicing, Impact, Metrics, From, Inout, and Security plug-ins—each addressing distinct facets of program correctness, runtime safety, data flow, and contract-based reasoning. This level of composability allows both academic researchers and practitioners to tailor the verification workflow to specific system constraints, from low-level memory safety proofs to high-assurance certification workflows. The tool’s open-source foundation and well-documented APIs have also fostered a vibrant community of contributors who continue to refine its mathematical soundness, usability, and scalability for modern C standards.

The credibility of Frama-C is further reinforced by its sustained adoption and validation in industrial contexts involving some of the world’s most demanding safety-critical sectors. Organizations such as Airbus, Thales, Dassault Aviation, Siemens, and CEA have integrated Frama-C into their verification pipelines to ensure compliance with stringent certification standards like DO-178C, ISO 26262, and IEC 61508, demonstrating its robustness and practical relevance beyond laboratory settings. Its blend of formal verification (through ACSL specifications and proof obligations) with advanced static analyses offers an effective compromise between mathematical rigor and engineering efficiency. Moreover, Frama-C’s open architecture has inspired numerous academic extensions and industrial plug-ins, evidencing its role not merely as a verification tool, but as a living research platform underpinning the evolution of formal methods in software engineering. The longevity, modular diversity, and proven dependability of Frama-C made it an ideal choice for our study, aligning perfectly with the goals of reproducibility, safety assurance, and formal traceability across all stages of C program verification.

2.5 | Traceability of Software Requirements

Traceability of software requirements is a cornerstone of reliable and maintainable software engineering, ensuring that every implemented component can be linked back to its originating requirement and verified throughout the development lifecycle. As software systems grow in complexity and evolve over time, maintaining accurate traceability becomes critical for validation,

[‡] <https://www.ibm.com/products/requirements-management/doors>

[§] <https://software.nasa.gov/software/ARC-18066-1>

[¶] <http://framenet.icsi.berkeley.edu/>

[#] https://qracorp.com/guides_checklists/the-easy-approach-to-requirements-syntax-ears/

^{||} <https://www.drisq.com/product-kapture>

^{**} <https://www.sonarsource.com/products/sonarqube/>

^{††} <https://www.frama-c.com/>

change impact analysis, and compliance with safety or quality standards. Moreover, modern software development practices—such as agile iteration, continuous integration, and model-driven engineering—demand dynamic and automated traceability mechanisms capable of adapting to evolving requirements and heterogeneous artifacts. The following body of research demonstrates a rich progression of methods, tools, and models designed to enhance traceability—from early static matrices and information retrieval techniques to intelligent, trust-based, and model-driven approaches that support formal reasoning and verification of software requirements.

A dynamic requirements traceability model is proposed in⁷⁷, enabling improved software quality through verification and validation of functional requirements. The model ensured software scalability as well, dealing both small and large-sized projects. A novel model for traceability and verification in the early development phase is presented in⁷⁸. Adaptability to requirement changes is improvised in the model and its impact is assessed.⁷⁹ provided a comprehensive review of software requirements traceability, covering key elements, challenges, and techniques. The study classified traceability approaches and highlighted prospects for future research.

The empirical analysis of requirements completeness is performed in⁸⁰. By enforcing completeness in requirements ensured reduced defect rates. Here, traceability metrics is produced and regression analysis is performed to quantify the software quality.⁸¹ introduced the RETRO tool for automating requirements traceability matrix (RTM) generation. The study showed that RETRO significantly improved accuracy and efficiency compared to manual tracing methods.⁸² proposed a hybrid approach combining VSM and BTM-GA to enhance traceability link generation. The method outperformed traditional IR techniques, improving recall and precision, particularly in agile development contexts.

Trustrace⁸³ is a trust-based traceability recovery approach. It leverages mined data from software repositories. In comparison to standard IR techniques, Trustrace improved precision and recall in traceability link retrieval.⁸⁴ applied deep learning for traceability, incorporating semantic understanding and domain knowledge. This is done using BI-GRU. It outperformed traditional approaches of VSM and LSI in terms of accuracy and effectiveness. A topology-based model-driven approach for backward requirements traceability is presented in⁸⁵, formalising specifications and establishing trace links between real-world functional units and software artifacts.

In order to manage software evolution process,⁸⁶ proposed an event-based traceability mechanism. The work reported performance improvement in change management by linking artifacts through an event service. It maintained consistency being deployed in distributed development environment. Tracebok⁸⁷ is a body of knowledge on software requirements traceability. The framework categorised traceability approaches and provided guidance for implementing traceability in software projects.⁸⁸ reviewed visualisation tools and techniques for software requirements traceability. The challenges emphasised were scalability and visual cluttering, providing insights of improved traceability visualisation.

In⁸⁹, Z notation is used to represent the SRS and design artifacts in order to establish the traceability of functional requirements. The SRS document originally used UML diagrams for requirement analysis and software design. Z notation established trace paths based on defined rules. A prototype framework based on XML is developed to trace the requirements in software design. The designed framework is named as RVVF (Requirement Verification and Validation Framework).⁹⁰ established the concept that terminology extraction can improve traceability from formal models to textual requirements. Cerbah et al.⁹⁰ presented a fully implemented system that analysed text corpora to generate hierarchically organised terminological resources and formal class hierarchies. These resources and formal class hierarchies are then communicated to the Troeps knowledge server via an XML stream. The system also enabled user validation of terminology elements and supports bidirectional linkage between the model and source documents. Survey paper⁹¹ examined requirements traceability, including definitions, challenges, and tools.⁹² represented a tool named TOOR - traceability of object-oriented requirements. The tool is based on the principles of hyper-programming and hyper-requirements.

Goknil et al.⁹³ addressed requirements and their relationships from a traceability perspective. It introduced a metamodel for requirements that included formally defined relation types. The relations are formalised using first-order logic to enable inference and consistency checking. A supporting tool demonstrated the approach on a real-world requirements document, helping to uncover hidden dependencies and detect contradictions.

2.6 | Formal Methods and Testing

A detailed examination of the interaction between formal specification techniques and software testing is presented in the 2009 ACM survey⁹⁴. The paper argues that formal descriptions of systems can significantly support the testing process. It introduces a classification of formal specification languages into several distinct categories. These include model-based methods such

as Z and VDM, languages grounded in finite-state representations like FSMs and state-charts, algebraic approaches such as OBJ, process algebraic notations like CSP and CCS, and hybrid methods that integrate both continuous and discrete system behaviours—although the latter are treated as outside the scope of the survey.

In practical applications, formal methods can contribute to testing by either enabling the automated generation of test cases or offering mechanisms to define precise test oracles. Executable specifications, in particular, may be subjected to model-checking techniques to assess conformance with desired properties. The theoretical underpinnings that link formal specifications with testing processes are also explored, with⁹⁵ offering foundational contributions—especially in identifying test selection assumptions that underpin the effectiveness of test generation. Each category of formalism is associated with its own techniques for producing relevant test artefacts.

Model-Based: In this category, testing often involves partitioning the input domain using assumptions about uniform system behaviour within each partition. Logical expressions—frequently cast in disjunctive normal form—are used to define these partitions and guide automation. Further approaches include domain analysis techniques that focus on identifying critical boundaries for functions and operators. Additionally, refinement-based testing and mutation techniques are discussed as part of this landscape. Although highly suitable for defining test oracles, model-based methods are often limited in their ability to automatically generate tests without the assistance of theorem-proving tools.

Finite State-Based: Testing approaches that rely on finite-state representations frequently define correctness in terms of language-based conformance between the implementation and its specification. A common strategy involves using a fault model to constrain the number of system states considered. Test generation techniques initially focus on deterministic finite-state machines, before expanding to address partial and non-deterministic forms. While these methods offer structured ways to derive test suites, the primary challenge lies in managing the combinatorial growth in possible state sequences.

Process Algebras: Systems described using process algebra are typically interpreted through labelled transition systems (LTS), which can be infinite. To address this, state space reduction techniques are often employed. In many respects, the methods and challenges of testing in this domain resemble those found in finite-state approaches, particularly with regard to scalability and complexity management.

Algebraic: Algebraic specifications are especially well-suited to object-oriented software. Test cases in this setting may be derived either from the syntactic structure of operations or from the logical axioms that define their intended behaviours. This method provides a strong formal basis for validation, although transforming abstract axioms into executable test procedures requires further elaboration and interpretation. The survey places particular emphasis on the value of automated reasoning tools in supporting test activities. Model checkers are highlighted as being capable of producing counterexamples when temporal properties are not satisfied, which can subsequently be re-purposed as test cases. Similarly, properties defined in temporal logic can guide the construction of structured test sequences.

Formal Tools: Isabelle/HOL is a powerful theorem prover based on higher-order logic. It features robust automation, a large repository of verified theorems, and tools for interactive proof construction. The system allows formal reasoning about complex mathematical properties and software systems, offering both depth and flexibility in its approach. Frama-C is a modular platform designed for the formal analysis of C code. It supports ACSL (ANSI-C Specification Language) for specifying expected behaviour and includes plug-ins for static analysis, verification, and integration with theorem provers. This makes it highly applicable to domains that demand rigorous validation of software correctness.

There has been significant progress in the use of probabilistic techniques for formal verification^{96,97,98}. Probabilistic model-checking focuses on evaluating how likely a system is to meet certain criteria, rather than delivering absolute verdicts. A comprehensive overview of developments in this area is provided in⁹⁹, particularly in the field of statistical model-checking, which offers scalable solutions for analysing stochastic systems in practical contexts. Promela is a modelling language aimed at the representation of concurrent systems. It is paired with the SPIN model checker, which is widely used in both academic and industrial settings. A supporting tool, Modex, can automatically extract Promela models from C code. SPIN evaluates properties defined in linear-time temporal logic (LTL), and when verification fails, the counterexamples it provides can be used to create test cases. Its command-line interface makes it suitable for automation and integration into larger tool-chains.

TLA+ offers a mathematical framework for specifying systems, particularly those involving concurrency. It emphasises logical precision using simple mathematical constructs. PlusCal provides a more familiar, algorithm-like syntax that compiles directly into TLA+, enabling a smoother transition for developers accustomed to pseudocode-style representations.

Deductive Verification is a formal verification technique that systematically proves program correctness by generating and discharging logical conditions derived from the program's specification. Unlike testing or model checking, which explore execution paths or system states, deductive verification relies on mathematical reasoning to ensure that every possible execution

satisfies the intended properties. Typically, this approach involves annotating code with preconditions, postconditions, and invariants, which are then translated into verification conditions (VCs). SMT solvers and theorem provers are used to automatically or semi-automatically discharge these conditions, providing strong guarantees of correctness when proofs succeed. This methodology is particularly effective for critical software domains, such as safety-critical embedded systems, where runtime errors or logical flaws can have severe consequences.

Recent developments in deductive verification have focused on improving automation, scalability, and solver integration. Modern SMT solvers, such as Z3, Alt-Ergo, CVC4, and CVC5, enable efficient reasoning over arithmetic, pointers, arrays, and quantified expressions, which are common in real-world programs. Toolchains like Frama-C leverage these solvers to translate high-level specifications into proof obligations, allowing verification engineers to focus on specifying program intent rather than manual proof construction. Additionally, advances in solver strategies, heuristics, and preprocessing techniques have reduced the incidence of timeouts and improved success rates on complex verification conditions, making deductive verification more practical for larger codebases. Together, these innovations are pushing deductive verification toward a more automated, reliable, and widely applicable paradigm in formal software verification.

3 | METHODOLOGY OF INITIAL EXPERIMENTS

This section outlines the methodology used to conduct our initial experiments aimed at assessing the behavior of automated test-generation and verification tools under controlled conditions. The approach is grounded in a representative example provided by PathCrawler and guided by prompt templates adapted from prior work. Our objective here is to establish a clear and reproducible experimental setup that illustrates how the tools respond to structured inputs before extending the evaluation to larger and more diverse datasets. The Frama-C platform is configured and executed within a Linux environment running on Windows Subsystem for Linux (WSL 2), hosted on a Windows 11 system equipped with an Intel Core Ultra 5 125U processor (3.60 GHz) and 32 GB of RAM (31.5 GB usable) operating under a 64-bit architecture. The procedures detailed in the following subsections define the basis for the empirical analyses that appear later in the paper.

3.1 | Experimental Re-Simulation and Verification of `TriType.c`

We re-simulated the methodology presented in⁸ by applying it to the `TriType.c` program, selected from the PathCrawler tool in the Frama-C ecosystem. The workflow integrated Large Language Models (LLMs) with symbolic outputs from PathCrawler and EVA to automatically generate ACSL specifications.

FIGURE 3 Methodology of the initial experiments following the approach of⁸, combining LLM with symbolic analysis tools in the Frama-C ecosystem. The workflow integrates path-based I/O examples and verification outputs to guide the generation of context-aware ACSL specifications.

PathCrawler provided path-based input/output examples that guided the LLM toward producing semantically accurate annotations. Table 1 shows the tool’s output. Our ongoing plan includes experiments with simple and complex programs featuring diverse control structures, enabling evaluation of the methodology’s generality.

The function under test is shown below.

```

/* Should return the type of the triangle
   which has sides of these lengths.
   3 = not a triangle
   2 = equilateral triangle
   1 = isosceles triangle
   0 = other triangle
*/

```

```

int Tritype(double i, double j, double k){
  int trityp = 0;
  if (i < 0.0 || j < 0.0 || k < 0.0)           // line 10
    return 3;
  if (i + j <= k || j + k <= i || k + i <= j) // line 12
    return 3;
  if (i == j) trityp = trityp + 1;           // line 14
  if (i == k) trityp = trityp + 1;           // line 15
  if (j == k) trityp = trityp + 1;           // line 16
  if (trityp >= 2)                            // line 17
    trityp = 2;
  return trityp;
}

```

TABLE 1 Output of the Pathcrawler for TriType Example

Test Case	i	j	k	Return Value	Path	Path Predicate
1	-196	364	18	3	tritype.c:+10	$i < 0$
2	260	364	18	3	tritype.c:-10:-10b:-10c:-12:-12b:+12c	$i \geq 0; j \geq 0; k \geq 0; (j+i) > k; (k+j) > i; (i+k) = < j$
3	197	940	1087	0	tritype.c:-10:-10b:-10c:-12:-12b:-12c:-14:-15:-16:-17	$i \geq 0; j \geq 0; k \geq 0; (j+i) > k; (k+j) > i; (i+k) > j; i < > j; i < > k; j < > k$
4	887	986	986	1	tritype.c:-10:-10b:-10c:-12:-12b:-12c:-14:-15:+16:-17	$i \geq 0; j \geq 0; k \geq 0; (j+i) > k; (k+j) > i; (i+k) > j; i < > j; i < > k; j = k$
5	952	990	952	1	tritype.c:-10:-10b:-10c:-12:-12b:-12c:-14:+15:-16:-17	$i \geq 0; j \geq 0; k \geq 0; (j+i) > k; (k+j) > i; (i+k) > j; i < > j; i = k; j < > k$
6	108	108	177	1	tritype.c:-10:-10b:-10c:-12:-12b:-12c:+14:-15:-16:-17	$i \geq 0; j \geq 0; k \geq 0; (j+i) > k; (k+j) > i; (i+k) > j; i = j; i < > k; j < > k$
7	646	646	646	2	tritype.c:-10:-10b:-10c:-12:-12b:-12c:+14:+15:+16:+17	$i \geq 0; j \geq 0; k \geq 0; (j+i) > k; (k+j) > i; (i+k) > j; i = j; i = k$
8	232	67	158	3	tritype.c:-10:-10b:-10c:-12:+12b	$i \geq 0; j \geq 0; k \geq 0; (j+i) > k; (k+j) = < i$
9	96	457	1530	3	tritype.c:-10:-10b:-10c:+12	$i \geq 0; j \geq 0; k \geq 0; (j+i) = < k$
10	260	364	-886	3	tritype.c:-10:-10b:+10c	$i \geq 0; j \geq 0; k < 0$
11	260	-533	18	3	tritype.c:-10:+10b	$i \geq 0; j < 0$

PathCrawler achieved 100% branch coverage while generating 11 test cases, all marked “unknown.” This outcome suggests that execution paths were traversed correctly, yet verdict classification failed due to incomplete postconditions or ambiguous return-value specifications. Of 19 identified paths, 11 were feasible and eight infeasible. The coverage demonstrates effective instrumentation, though the absence of successful verdicts highlights the need for refined oracles and explicit assertions. The dataset nevertheless provides rich insights into path feasibility and constraint diversity across valid, invalid, and boundary inputs.

Reproducing the baseline from⁸ revealed that Frama-C’s analysis, using Alt-Ergo, Z3, CVC4, and CVC5, generated only two trivial verification goals—termination and unreachable—both successfully proven. This confirms structural soundness and absence of infinite loops or dead code but exposes the limits of minimal ACSL specification. The lack of user-defined pre/postconditions and missing `assigns` clauses restricted verification to syntactic validation, leaving functional correctness untested. While no runtime errors were reported, the omission of Run-Time Error (RTE) guards means potential overflows or edge-case failures remain unchecked. Overall, all solvers performed equivalently under these basic conditions, verifying the function’s structural integrity but offering little semantic assurance.

The PathCrawler-augmented version (pp. 21-22,⁸) introduced detailed ACSL annotations, generating 20 verification goals—18 derived from explicit pre/postconditions plus the standard structural checks. This enriched specification significantly increased solver complexity. While all provers confirmed termination and reachability, only Alt-Ergo and CVC5 proved 15 goals, whereas Z3 and CVC4 proved 13 each. Unverified goals predominantly involved disjunction-heavy triangle classification logic and arithmetic inequalities. These failures stem from the difficulty solvers face in reasoning over conditional branches with subtle numeric constraints. The results underscore that symbolic-annotation synergy improves verification depth but stresses solver capacity. Integrating stronger lemma decomposition or intermediate assertions may enhance success rates in future iterations.

TABLE 2 Prover Results Comparison (with Baseline and Pathcrawler Output Augmented Prompt)

(a) Baseline Example1-Tritype.c				(b) Pathcrawler Augmented Example1-Tritype.c				
Prover	Total Goals	Proved	Notes	Prover	Total Goals	Proved	Failed Type	Failed Count
Alt-Ergo	2	2	All default goals proved	Z3	20	13	Timeout	7
Z3	2	2	All default goals proved	Alt-Ergo	20	15	Timeout	5
CVC4	2	2	All default goals proved	CVC4	20	13	Unknown	7
CVC5	2	2	All default goals proved	CVC5	20	15	Timeout	5

3.2 | Empirical Evaluation on Frama-C iFM2024 tutorial program set

To evaluate the effectiveness of different SMT solvers in deductive verification, four provers—Z3, Alt-Ergo, CVC4, and CVC5—were tested on 36 representative C programs from the Frama-C tutorial suite. Each example includes arithmetic, pointer, and array manipulation constructs verified using the WP plugin. Table 3 presents a sample subset illustrating the comparative proof coverage and goal completion across these provers.

TABLE 3 Sample verification outcomes across four SMT provers (subset of 36 code snippets).

C File	Goals	Z3	Alt-Ergo	CVC4	CVC5	Timeouts	Timeout %	Success Rate %
01-abs-2.c	6	6/6	6/6	6/6	6/6	0	0.0	100.0
02-max-1.c	7	5/7	5/7	5/7	5/7	2	28.6	71.4
03-max_ptr-1.c	8	6/8	6/8	6/8	6/8	2	25.0	75.0
04-swap-0.c	8	4/8	4/8	4/8	4/8	4	50.0	50.0
06-max_abs-3.c	13	13/13	13/13	13/13	13/13	0	0.0	100.0

All four SMT provers—Z3, Alt-Ergo, CVC4, and CVC5—exhibited comparable verification performance across the tested benchmarks, consistently solving most arithmetic, pointer, and array-related goals. Here, we are including table for reference, reporting output of Z3. Timeout rates were generally low, and differences in success rates were minimal, indicating that each solver can reliably handle typical verification conditions. While minor variations appeared on more complex or nested constructs, no prover showed a clear advantage, suggesting that any of these tools can serve effectively in automated verification workflows within the Frama-C ecosystem. The execution times taken by each prover is given in figure 4.

FIGURE 4 Graph of Execution Times of Alt-Ergo, Z3, CVC4 and CVC5

4 | EMPIRICAL EVALUATION OF FRAMA-C EVA AND RTE FOR ACSL ANNOTATION AND STATIC VERIFICATION

In this part of the study, we present a comprehensive empirical evaluation of the Frama-C *EVA* (Evolved Value Analysis) and *RTE* (Runtime Error) plugins, which support the creation and verification of formal specifications for C programs. The goal of this evaluation is to examine how these tools contribute to the automation of specification generation through ACSL (ANSI/ISO C Specification Language) annotations and to assess their practical capabilities when applied to a curated benchmark of real C code. The hardware used kept same as specified in paragraph 1, Section 3.

A benchmark consisting of fifty C programs, each exhibiting distinct structural complexity, was adopted without modification from a publicly available GitHub repository^{‡‡} used for prompt engineering reported in⁸. Following the design of the original work, these programs were grouped into three predefined categories: (i) correct implementations, (ii) implementations exhibiting obvious differences between function variants, and (iii) implementations with subtle differences in their function bodies. Each of the fifty base programs was analyzed across these three categories, yielding a total of 150 evaluated instances. This multi-category organization enables the systematic study of tool behavior across a controlled spectrum of semantic and syntactic variations.

Within this setup, the *EVA* plugin performed sound abstract interpretation to analyze each program’s control flow and data dependencies, identifying potential runtime anomalies and verifying functional behavior. In parallel, the *RTE* plugin automatically generated ACSL annotations to express inferred preconditions, postconditions, and invariants that capture candidate formal contracts. All outputs—*EVA* logs, inferred specifications, and analysis results—were collected and organized for subsequent tabular presentation and comparative study.

This empirical analysis is motivated by the broader goal of improving automation in formal methods workflows. Reliable software systems, especially those deployed in safety-critical or high-assurance domains, require early defect detection and strong guarantees of correctness. While formal methods provide these guarantees, their adoption remains limited due to the substantial effort required to create, interpret, and maintain mathematically precise specifications. Developers are typically expected to not only implement functionality but also encode behavioral intent in specification languages interpretable by automated verifiers. This task demands specialized expertise and significant additional development time, representing a key barrier to widespread industrial uptake. Tools such as Frama-C, and specifically the *EVA* and *RTE* plugins, are designed to mitigate this challenge by bridging the gap between implementation and formal reasoning.

The findings from this evaluation are contextualized within a broader methodological framework that integrates benchmark-driven analysis with dataset-based validation. In addition to the empirical evaluation of Frama-C plugins, several datasets were incorporated to assess the consistency and scalability of specification generation and verification processes.

Evaluation Metrics. Evaluation across all datasets employed a consistent set of quantitative and qualitative metrics. These included specification accuracy (through manual review and ground-truth comparison), verification success rate (based on Frama-C WP outcomes), model completeness (coverage of preconditions, postconditions, and frame conditions), and context sensitivity (measured through performance changes under varying prompt scopes). Solver coverage was quantified in terms of goals proven per solver. All datasets, experimental prompts, synthesized specifications, and verification outcomes have been released in an open-access GitHub repository to facilitate transparency, reproducibility, and collaborative exploration.

4.1 | EVA Analysis and Results

The *EVA* plugin’s analysis evaluates the extent to which Frama-C can detect and classify potential runtime issues through abstract interpretation. A consolidated overview of the *EVA* results across the three categories—Correct, Obvious, and Subtle—is presented in Table 4. Figure 5(a) summarises the total number of alarms produced per program category. Correct programs yield the fewest alarms overall, typically limited to minor boundary or division-by-zero checks. Programs with obvious functional differences show a moderate increase in alarm count, as *EVA* identifies deviations in data flow and control structures that could lead to runtime faults. Subtle-difference programs, by contrast, exhibit the highest number of alarms, reflecting *EVA*’s sensitivity to small but semantically significant variations that introduce uncertain execution paths. This trend illustrates *EVA*’s precision in differentiating between benign and critical deviations in program behavior.

^{‡‡} https://github.com/ggranberry/intent_dataset

TABLE 4 EVA Category-wise Result Summary

Category	Files	Mean Coverage (%)	Median Coverage (%)	Mean Alarms	Median Alarms	Success Rate
Correct	52	75.00	96.0	38.66	3.0	0.308
Obvious	60	77.73	97.0	0.68	0.0	0.650
Subtle	53	58.84	88.0	7.59	3.0	0.623

The nature of detected alarms is illustrated in Figure 5(b), which categorizes them by type, including uninitialized memory access, division by zero, invalid pointer dereference, and out-of-bounds array indexing. Across all categories, pointer-related alarms dominate—indicating EVA’s conservative bias toward ensuring memory safety. Division and bounds-related alarms occur less frequently but tend to cluster in subtle-difference programs, where small logical shifts affect variable ranges. The distribution highlights EVA’s layered reasoning approach: it prioritizes memory safety while maintaining comprehensive coverage of arithmetic and control-flow conditions.

Figure 5(c) presents the statement coverage achieved by EVA, representing the proportion of executable statements analyzed and instrumented with abstract value information. Coverage remains highest for correct programs—often exceeding 90%—thanks to well-defined data flow and stable control paths. Coverage decreases for programs with obvious and subtle differences, where undefined behaviors, pointer aliasing, or non-deterministic inputs limit full propagation of abstract domains. This reduction reveals the inherent trade-off between precision and scalability in static value analysis, particularly when handling complex pointer manipulations or dynamic structures.

Finally, Figure 5(d) aggregates the success rate of EVA’s analysis, indicating the proportion of alarms successfully discharged as non-critical or safe after propagation and refinement. Correct programs achieved the highest success rates, confirming that EVA can confidently validate the absence of runtime errors. Obvious-difference cases retained moderate success rates, while subtle-difference programs displayed lower rates due to compounded uncertainties and partially explored states. Importantly, no category resulted in complete analysis failure, demonstrating EVA’s robustness in handling diverse program structures and maintaining soundness under all evaluation conditions.

In summary, this section presented a detailed empirical investigation of Frama-C’s EVA plugin as an automated static analyzer for detecting potential runtime errors and assessing program reliability. By evaluating a benchmark of fifty C programs across three categories, the study demonstrated EVA’s effectiveness in identifying subtle behavioral discrepancies and ensuring soundness under diverse control-flow conditions. The results confirm EVA’s practical role as a foundational tool for static verification, complementing later proof-oriented analyses. They also highlight current challenges related to analysis coverage and precision, motivating further work on domain refinement and hybrid symbolic approaches to improve the scalability and expressiveness of Frama-C based analyses.

4.2 | RTE Analysis and Results

The Runtime Error (RTE) plugin in Frama-C operates as an automated assertion generator and runtime property checker, complementing EVA’s abstract interpretation by directly targeting sources of undefined or unsafe behavior such as overflows, invalid memory access, and division by zero. Whereas EVA reconstructs abstract value domains, RTE instruments the program with concrete checks and passes the generated proof obligations to SMT solvers. This study presents a quantitative evaluation of RTE across the three benchmark families *correct*, *obvious-difference*, and *subtle-difference* focusing on solver stability, proof coverage, and verification scalability.

For the *correct* program category (Figure 6), proof success rates for Alt-Ergo, Z3, CVC4, and CVC5 approach full coverage, confirming RTEs strong alignment with provable safety properties. Solver outcome heatmaps are uniformly saturated, reflecting consistent convergence, and timeout counts are negligible. Overall, these results demonstrate stable and efficient verification for programs without functional differences.

For the *obvious-difference* category (Figure 7), proof success rates are slightly lower, and solver outcome heatmaps show localized patches of failure at array-bound or nested arithmetic checks. Timeout counts increase modestly due to denser assertion sets. These observations indicate a moderate increase in verification complexity, though partial proofs remain common across solvers.

For the *subtle-difference* category (Figure 8), proof success rates diverge significantly across solvers, with Alt-Ergo generally performing better on arithmetic-heavy proofs. Solver outcome heatmaps appear fragmented, revealing clusters of challenging assertions. Timeout counts increase substantially, reflecting higher semantic coupling among assertions. Despite

FIGURE 5 EVA analysis results across the three program categories: (a) distribution of alarm types, (b) total alarms detected, (c) statement coverage of analyzed code, and (d) overall success rate of EVA’s runtime error analysis.

this, partial proofs are typically present, demonstrating that RTE-generated assertions remain valid and useful for downstream verification.

Across all categories, verification cost under RTE is influenced more by assertion heterogeneity and semantic coupling than by program size, with proof-time dispersion increasing super-linearly with functional deviation. Solver heterogeneity highlights the value of multi-prover strategies, as each solver contributes unique strengths in arithmetic reasoning, quantifier handling, and pointer alias resolution. The consistently high success rates for correct programs confirm RTE as a dependable source of automatically generated runtime contracts, suitable as a foundation for deductive verification with WP. Overall, RTE proves effective both as a runtime-safety analyzer and as a benchmark for solver scalability in formal verification workflows.

4.3 | PathCrawler Experiments and Progress

PathCrawler is a Frama-C plugin designed for automatic generation of test cases based on path exploration of C programs. During the course of our research, several challenges emerged that required careful resolution in order to integrate PathCrawler into our formal verification workflow alongside EVA and RTE.

Initial Barriers and Setup: The online version of PathCrawler proved unreliable, repeatedly failing during attempted executions. This reinforced the need for a local configuration to ensure stable and repeatable experimentation. The plugin was independently configured and compiled with Frama-C, resolving dependency and environment issues, particularly those related to ECLiPSe-CLP, the underlying constraint solver. Initial runs with example programs, including `Swap` and `RunningSum`, were partially successful, but outputs were inconsistent and incomplete. Compilation issues were addressed by updating PathCrawler to a version compatible with the latest ECLiPSe-CLP and recompiling the sources, which resulted in a functioning local installation.

FIGURE 6 RTE runtime verification results for *correct* program category. Subfigures show (a) standard deviation of QED times, (b) proof success rate, (c) solver performance heatmap, and (d) solver timeouts.

Tool Limitations: PathCrawler imposes several inherent restrictions on the programs it can handle. The current version cannot process input operations reading from the console or files (`scanf`, `fscanf`, etc.); floating-point types (`float`)-`double` is partially supported but computations involving trigonometric functions slow down constraint resolution significantly; explicit or implicit casts beyond integer-to-floating-point types, including pointer casts; assembly code embedded in functions; pointers to functions used as input parameters, or formal parameters which are themselves functions; recursive structures or recursive functions; `void*` pointers as function inputs; functions with variable-length argument lists; functions whose source code is unavailable, including standard library functions, which may prevent correct test case generation; and integer constants exceeding the representable range for the target type.

These constraints necessitated careful preparation of the dataset and highlighted that programs successfully analyzed with EVA or RTE may not yield test cases with PathCrawler without modifications.

Dataset Modification: To work around these restrictions, the dataset of C files was systematically modified. Interrupt signals generated during PathCrawler test case generation were traced to unhandled code constructs, and a Python script was developed to preprocess each C file. The script encapsulated the function under test together with a `main` function, suppressed unsupported operations, and ensured compatibility with PathCrawlers limitations. With these modifications, test case generation succeeded for a subset of the dataset. Initially, only four out of twenty files produced valid test cases without errors. Iterative refinement of the preprocessing script enabled successful generation for fifteen out of twenty files in the `correct/basic` subfolder.

Path Coverage and Generator Options: One major bottleneck arose from PathCrawlers default coverage strategy. By default, it attempts to explore all possible paths, which frequently resulted in zero successful test cases. To address this, the OCaml wrapper functions were modified and a new `-pc-max-paths N` option was implemented, allowing the user to limit the number of explored paths. Despite this, the `.pl` scripts responsible for generating path exploration commands still enforced the "all paths" coverage mode. A practical workaround involved specifying the function body for analysis and disabling standard library translation, using the following command:

```
frama-c -pc -wp -pc-branches-func "functionBody"
-no-frama-c-stdlib -variadic-no-translation file.c > output_file.txt
```


FIGURE 7 RTE runtime verification results for *obvious-difference* program category. Subfigures show (a) standard deviation of QED times, (b) proof success rate, (c) solver performance heatmap, and (d) solver timeouts.

This approach permitted selective path exploration and the generation of traces for functions that did not contain unsupported constructs such as pointers or external library calls (`printf`, `memset`). Manual editing of C files was sometimes required to ensure compatibility.

Test Case Generation: After these adjustments, PathCrawler successfully generated test cases across multiple programs. For example, the `binarySearch` and `tritype` functions produced seven and ten test cases, respectively, when executed with:

```
frama-c -pc -pc-drivers -lib-entry -main "quicksort"
-no-frama-c-stdlib -variadic-no-translation quicksort.c
```

The `-pc-drivers` option enabled automatic generation of test drivers, which was previously unavailable. Additionally, the `-pc-iter-limit N` option was tested to limit the number of iterations during test case generation, providing better control over execution time and resource usage. Successful generation was particularly observed for functions without external dependencies or complex pointer manipulations.

Pathcrawler Output Log for QuickSort function: The PathCrawler (Frama-C) automatic test-generation session for the `quicksort` function completed normally and generated a total of eleven test cases intended to cover all feasible execution paths. The session explored 110 total execution paths or partial paths, out of which 11 were feasible and successfully associated with generated test cases, while the remaining 99 were classified as infeasible. The oracle used during execution was unable to determine correctness, and therefore each of the eleven test cases received the verdict unknown. No user assertions were violated, and the process finished within approximately one second of total execution time.

Each generated test case is associated with a path prefix identifier and a corresponding symbolic execution trace through `quicksort.c`, expressed in PathCrawler's path-notation format (e.g., `-11a`, `+23`, `-36b`, etc.). These traces collectively represent the distinct feasible control-flow paths encountered during symbolic exploration. Test cases differ primarily in the structure and repetition of their pivot-comparison and recursive-call path segments, revealing how PathCrawler unfolds and prunes the `quicksort` recursion under varying symbolic constraints. All generated test cases exhibit the unknown verdict solely because the oracle for validating output correctness was not provided or was insufficient for classification.

external library calls, or unsupported casts often required code adaptation. Additionally, fine-tuning the number of paths explored was crucial to avoid long execution times and incomplete outputs. Overall, these challenges underscore the importance of dataset preprocessing and careful configuration when integrating PathCrawler into a formal verification workflow.

Ongoing work focuses on scaling PathCrawler experiments to larger datasets, integrating its outputs with analyses from EVA and RTE, and exploring the combination with AI-assisted testing tools such as Qwen and Ollama. The goal is to create a unified pipeline that leverages automated test generation, runtime property checking, and static analysis to improve coverage and reliability of software verification.

5 | CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The attempt to position large language models (LLMs) within the practices of formal specification and verification raises philosophical questions about the nature of meaning, inference, and the limits of mechanised reasoning. At its core, formal verification demands a commitment to determinacy: every symbol must denote a precise concept, every statement must resolve to a truth value relative to a well-defined semantics, and every proof must be justified through inferential steps that are both sound and explicit. Natural language, by contrast, lives in a domain of interpretive openness, shaped by context, intention, and tacit knowledge. When an LLM maps informal narratives onto formal specifications, it is not merely performing translation; it is mediating between two radically different conceptions of meaning—one probabilistic, fluid, and distributed, while the other is deductive, sharp-edged, and grounded in mathematical ontology. The friction between these modalities is not incidental but structural: it reflects the philosophical divergence between linguistic practice in human communities and the logical formalism required for machine-checked reasoning. Addressing this tension requires more than improving models or datasets; it requires a deeper theoretical account of how semantic commitments are constructed, represented, and validated across these distinct epistemic regimes.

A pressing difficulty arises from the absence of comprehensive datasets that faithfully bridge natural-language intentions with formal logical constructs in a way that reflects real-world complexity. However, the problem is not simply a lack of data; it is a lack of epistemically coherent corpora that map human concepts to formal invariants with philosophical integrity. Data of this sort is not merely collected but curated through informed judgement about meaning, relevance, and abstraction. In constructing such datasets, one confronts basic questions: What constitutes a faithful formalisation of a requirement? How do we distinguish essential semantic content from incidental narrative structure? How should ambiguity, intentional vagueness, or normative assumptions be represented—if at all—within a formal system that presupposes exactness? These questions reflect longstanding tensions in the philosophy of language and logic: the boundary between description and prescription, the nature of implicit commitments, and the status of meaning as inherently social rather than purely symbolic. Any dataset capable of supporting rigorous research into LLM-driven specification must therefore grapple with these philosophical issues rather than treat them as mere engineering obstacles.

Another deep challenge concerns the fragmentation of the verification tool ecosystem and the implications this has for theories of representation. Different verification tools encode different worldviews i.e. different logics, abstraction mechanisms, and ontological commitments. Integrating LLMs into this landscape requires understanding these tools not as interchangeable mechanical components but as embodiments of distinct philosophical positions about computation, proof, and correctness. The absence of a unifying intermediate representation is thus more than a technical inconvenience; it is symptomatic of deeper theoretical disunity. A future in which LLMs and symbolic tools operate in a reciprocal, dialectical relationship—where neural inferences are shaped by logical constraints and symbolic proofs benefit from inductive heuristics—requires a synthesis between two kinds of reasoning historically seen as opposed: the inductive and the deductive, the heuristic and the foundational, the statistical and the formal. Developing such a hybrid architecture invites reflection on classical debates in the philosophy of mathematics regarding the interaction between intuition, pattern recognition, and formal proof such as in⁴.

A further challenge lies in maintaining coherent traceability among evolving artefacts across the software lifecycle. Here the difficulty is not solely engineering complexity but the philosophical problem of identity over time: when a requirement changes, what exactly has changed—the words, the intention, the behavioural commitments, or the conceptual boundaries of the system itself? Traceability seeks to preserve a chain of meaning across transformations, yet automated systems struggle to model meaning as something that evolves holistically rather than as a collection of isolated statements. LLMs can produce plausible relational mappings, but plausibility is not a substitute for normatively valid justification. Addressing this issue requires

rethinking artefact evolution in terms of refinement as a philosophical relation: a structured correspondence between successive conceptualisations of a system, anchored in stable semantic invariants. Only then can traceability be something more than a mechanical bookkeeping exercise; it becomes a discipline of preserving conceptual coherence across time.

Finally, the question of explainability touches the deepest philosophical concerns of all: What does it mean for a system to understand, justify, or warrant its assertions? Current LLM explanations are narrative reconstructions rather than transparent accounts of reasoning. In formal verification, such narratives are insufficient, because justification is not rhetorical but logical; it must appeal to structures that stand independently of the explainer. For LLM-generated specifications to be trustworthy, explanations must expose assumptions, uncertainties, and inferential steps in a way that respects the norms of formal reasoning. This invites an inquiry into whether explanations generated by probabilistic models can ever possess the normative force of logical argumentation. It raises a larger philosophical question about the relationship between human concepts of understanding and the operational behaviours of statistical models: To what extent can an artefact that lacks grounding in intentional states produce explanations that satisfy epistemic norms rather than mimic their surface forms?

Collectively, these challenges point toward a future research agenda that is not merely interdisciplinary but fundamentally philosophical. The integration of LLMs into specification and verification is not simply an engineering problem but an opportunity to reconsider the foundations of meaning, inference, and correctness in computational systems. Progress in this domain will require reconciling probabilistic characterisations of language with formal structures of logic, developing representations that mediate between human concepts and machine semantics, and cultivating tools that respect both the precision of formalism and the richness of natural-language reasoning. In this sense, the challenge is not only to advance verification technology but to deepen our conceptual understanding of how meaning becomes formal and how formal structures can faithfully represent human intentions in the design of correct and trustworthy systems.

5.1 | Embedding LLMs in the Specification Generation

5.1.1 | Planned Evaluation of Prompting Strategies

A systematic and quantitative evaluation of prompting strategies is the central part of our planned research. In particular, we intend to compare zero-shot, one-shot, few-shot, and Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting across both assertion-level and full-contract generation tasks. Prior work in the literature related to prompt engineering suggests that prompt type and articulation can significantly influence specification quality. However, a comprehensive evaluation requires a larger and more diverse benchmark than we currently report.

Future experiments will therefore assess prompt sensitivity using precision, recall, and F1-based correctness metrics, and investigate robustness under small variations of prompt formulation. We anticipate that assertion-level tasks will prove more stable under prompt rephrasing, whereas full-contract synthesis may show higher variability—an observation that motivates deeper analysis in follow-up work. Our current contribution is to highlight the importance of prompt design in our work and to outline how this dimension will be systematically investigated going forward.

5.1.2 | Human-in-the-Loop Integration and Interoperability Considerations

Our experiments currently implement the early stages of a human-in-the-loop process through manual review. In both the Tritype baseline and PathCrawler-augmented workflows, every LLM-generated ACSL specification was checked by at least one author with formal methods expertise. This review ensured (i) semantic alignment with intended behavior, (ii) logical completeness, and (iii) iterative refinement by feeding corrected fragments back into the prompts. Although active learning is not yet integrated, our project approach anticipates it: revised specifications, along with their source code and verification results, can be versioned and selectively reused for retraining or fine-tuning.

Figure 10 shows our proposed workflow based on the state of the art and figured out challenges in Section 5. Natural language requirements and domain ontologies form the input, grounding the LLM in the target context. Different prompt strategies (zero-shot, few-shot, and Chain-of-Thought) shape how inputs are presented for specification generation. Outputs are stored in a *tool-neutral intermediate format* (JSON-LD), which can be translated into the syntax required by verification tools. These tools check the generated specifications, while symbolic reasoning provides constraint-based feedback that helps refine them. Human reviewers remain part of the loop, validating results, focusing on manageable units, and collecting useful

FIGURE 10 Proposed Workflow for the VERIFYAI pipeline: Natural-language requirements and domain ontologies are combined with prompt strategies to generate formal specifications via LLMs. Outputs in JSON-LD feed verification tools, with symbolic and human feedback refining results.

examples for future adaptation. The design is modular, so new reasoning engines, prompt methods, or domain adapters can be added without changing the overall pipeline.

For interoperability, the pipeline currently uses custom scripts to convert LLM outputs to tool-specific formats (e.g., ACSL for Frama-C, JML for OpenJML). While functional, this approach is not generalisable. As part of VERIFYAI, we plan to design a lightweight JSON-LD-based schema that maps to multiple formal languages. This would allow LLM outputs to be stored in a tool-agnostic format and exported to different targets, potentially supporting Frama-C, OpenJML, Dafny, and others with minimal per-tool changes.

5.1.3 | Symbolic Reasoning, Traceability, and Scalability Outlook

In our initial Tritype experiments, symbolic solvers were used only for post-generation verification. We see potential for tighter integration, where solver feedback—such as unsatisfiable path conditions—could guide the LLM during generation, reducing logical errors before verification. Currently, traceability relies on manual annotations linking specification fragments to source code and natural-language requirements. We are exploring semi-automated approaches where the LLM proposes initial links for human validation. These links could be stored in a graph database to support version-aware navigation and visual trace maps, which would be particularly valuable in regulated settings.

We aim to build datasets that combine real-world, diverse requirements with verified specifications and execution traces. Currently, we are curating a small seed set from open-source safety-critical software, supplemented with synthetic examples to cover edge cases. While synthetic data is useful, it lacks the nuances of industrial requirements, so mixed datasets appear most promising. VERIFYAI's prototype handles single-module programs well, but multi-module systems pose memory and latency challenges. To manage complexity, we plan to employ hierarchical specification synthesis, verifying each module independently prior to integration. Additionally, we aim to release an annotated subset of the dataset to support transparency and reproducibility.

5.1.4 | LLMs trustworthiness in the context of verification and validation

The survey research conducted in 2024¹⁰⁰ examines more than 370 research articles with a focus on trustworthiness of LLMs in context of verification and validation. As the survey is quite comprehensive, we describe the discussion in detail:

The survey¹⁰⁰ underscores that as large language models (LLMs) become more deeply integrated into mainstream applications and interact directly with end users, trustworthiness and safety emerge as critical challenges that surpass those faced by traditional machine learning models. Unlike conventional systems trained on curated datasets such as ImageNet, LLMs are typically trained on massive, unfiltered internet corpora, which introduces ethical, legal, and technical vulnerabilities. Chief among these are data privacy and copyright concerns, as LLMs may inadvertently memorize and reproduce sensitive or proprietary information extracted from online sources without authorization. Compounding the risk are emerging prompt injection and data extraction attacks, which can exploit the models learned associations to reveal private or confidential content. The survey stresses that these challenges demand multidisciplinary solutions—combining advances in machine learning security, data governance, privacy-preserving computation, and legal frameworks—to ensure responsible development and deployment of LLM-based systems.

Furthermore, the discussion emphasizes that the lag between LLM adoption and research on their trustworthiness represents a widening gap that must be urgently addressed. The paper calls for systematic investment in methods for transparency, interpretability, and accountability, highlighting that LLMs scale and autonomy amplify risks beyond those of standard AI models. It suggests that future research should move toward verifiable model behavior, formal safety guarantees, and ethical data sourcing, supported by stronger interdisciplinary collaboration among AI researchers, ethicists, and policymakers. In essence,¹⁰⁰ positions the pursuit of trustworthy LLMs not merely as a technical necessity but as a societal imperative, where ensuring privacy, fairness, and reliability becomes foundational to sustaining public confidence in AI systems.

6 | CONCLUSIONS

This study addresses the persistent challenge of translating informal, natural language requirements into formal specifications, a critical concern in safety-critical software domains such as aerospace, autonomous systems, and medical devices. By combining a comprehensive survey of state-of-the-art research with empirical evaluation of practical tools, the work demonstrates both the promise and current limitations of AI-driven specification generation. Our survey synthesizes approaches leveraging natural language processing, ontology-based domain modelling, software artefact reuse, and large language models (LLMs), highlighting effective methods for generating formal specifications compatible with various verification tools, including theorem provers and model checkers. This synthesis provides a structured overview of existing methodologies while identifying technical gaps, such as challenges in traceability, tool integration, and specification reuse, which remain critical for reliable automated formalisation.

The empirical component of the study reinforces these insights by evaluating Frama-C plugins, including the Runtime Error (RTE) and EVA analyzers, alongside the PathCrawler test generation tool. Experiments demonstrate the tools ability to infer assertions, generate ACSL specifications, detect runtime anomalies, and explore path feasibility for representative C programs. Observed limitations—such as solver instability, incomplete path coverage, and ambiguous or missing postconditions—highlight the necessity for careful dataset adaptation, selective path exploration, and human-guided configuration to achieve reliable results. These findings underscore that while automation significantly supports software correctness, human oversight and multi-tool orchestration remain essential in high-assurance workflows.

Looking forward, future work should focus on enhancing solver robustness, developing richer ACSL templates, and improving integration between AI-generated specifications and formal verification tools. Additionally, incorporating interactive feedback loops and cross-tool orchestration could further reduce human intervention and streamline traceable verification processes. Overall, this study lays the groundwork for intelligent, automated, and verifiable specification workflows, offering practical guidance for combining AI-driven formalisation with rigorous verification to advance the development of high-assurance software systems.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found at our GitHub repository https://github.com/arshadbeg/STVR-Submission_SupportingMaterial and https://github.com/arshadbeg/OVERLAY2025_SupportingDocs.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed equally in this research.

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USE OF AI-ASSISTED TOOLS

During **manuscript preparation**, we used the free versions of OpenAI’s GPT-4, GPT-4o-mini, and GPT-5 models—available at various points during the course of this research (January 2025 to November 2025)—solely for editorial assistance. Their use was for refining text, generating tables from our experimentally obtained results, and formatting content to comply with the Wiley submission template.

In “Methodology of literature survey” subsection, we mentioned, “To streamline the process of **locating strong contributions**, the AI-powered tool Elicit⁹ is used .. every suggested paper in this review is manually reviewed to ensure its relevance. This ensures that the final list excludes any unrelated or off-topic material. After the initial filtering, a manual review is performed to confirm the relevance and quality of each paper. Abstracts are first assessed to judge suitability. If the abstract lacks clarity or depth, a further examination of the full text is conducted.” Above statement makes clear that Elicit is used strictly for identifying candidate literature and does not contribute to any analysis, synthesis, or interpretation.

FINANCIAL DISCLOSURE

None reported.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no potential conflict of interests.

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TABLE 5 Classification of Surveyed Literature by Methodology

References	Classification
1, 2, 12, 13, 41, 29, 38, 8, 54, 101, 19, 61, 59, 33, 52, 18, 12, 13, 55, 52, 54, 35, 24, 25	Prompt-only
13, 12, 38, 59, 101	Prompt + Iterative / Human-in-loop / CoT
13, 12, 38, 59, 101	Prompt + Iterative / Human-in-loop / CoT
3, 44, 102, 37, 49, 38, 102, 11, 69	Fine-tuned
17, 18, 45, 103, 19, 52, 101, 10, 34, 22, 43, 30	Verifier-in-loop
27, 20, 13, 16, 74	Neuro-symbolic (LLM + SMT/Theorem Prover)
28, 47, 44, 5, 28, 47, 34	Baseline / Manual / Controlled NL
37, 104, 42, 21, 104, 100, 23, 36	Meta-analysis / Tool Support
46, 34	IDE Integration Proposal
70, 71, 73, 43, 69, 75, 76	Dataset / Benchmark
15	Conversational / Ontology Requirements Engineering

TABLE 6 Classification and Description of Surveyed Literature

Ref.	Tool / Work	Classification	Description
41	Domain Model Extractor	Fine-tuned	Generates domain models from NL requirements; evaluated in an industrial case study for performance and accuracy.
104	Symbolic NLP vs. ChatGPT	Prompt-only	Compares symbolic NLP and ChatGPT in generating correct JML from NL pre-conditions.
46	BPM-to-NL Translation	Prompt-only	Translates business process models to NL to support better stakeholder validation.
19	Lemur	Verifier-in-loop	Integrates LLMs with automated reasoners and defines sound transition rules for verification.
14	GPT-4o for VeriFast Verification	Verifier-in-loop	Assesses GPT-4o's performance in generating C specs for VeriFast; captures issues in functional correctness.
45	ARSENAL	Fine-tuned	Extracts requirements from NL and performs automatic verification.
7	Laurel for Dafny	Prompt-only + Verifier-in-loop	Automates generation of Dafny assertions to support SMT-based verification.
8	PathCrawler + EVA	Verifier-in-loop + Prompt	PathCrawler generates context-aware ACSL annotations; EVA reduces runtime errors in Frama-C.
39	NL to Temporal Logic Translation	Prompt-only	Automatically translates NL into temporal logic for formal verification.
20	Req2Spec	Prompt-only	Converts NL requirements into formal specs (e.g., HANFOR); 71% accuracy on BOSCH data.
26	AssertLLM	Multi-LLMs / Prompt-only	Uses 3 customized LLMs to generate assertions from hardware design specs; 89% correctness achieved.
18	SpecSyn	Fine-tuned	Synthesizes software specifications from NL, improving over prior tools by 21%.
17	n12spec	Prompt-only + Iterative Refinement	Iteratively generates formal specs from NL requirements, reducing ambiguity.
105	LLM-based Requirement Coverage	Prompt-only	Maps low-level requirements to high-level ones with 99.7% recall in coverage detection.
28	SpecLLM	Prompt-only	Uses LLMs to create and review VLSI design specs, enhancing chip documentation.
38	NL-to-LTL via LLMs	Prompt-only	Converts unstructured NL to NL-LTL pairs with 94.4% accuracy.
106	ANTONIO Toolkit	Verifier-in-loop	Introduces an NLP Verification Pipeline with metrics, gaps, and semantic subspace verification proposals.
12	GPT-3.5 for Code Verification	Prompt-only	Uses GPT-3.5 to verify code against requirements, providing feedback on requirement satisfaction.
29	GPT-4o + Claude for Smart Grid	Verifier-in-loop	Applies GPT-4o and Claude 3.5 for smart grid requirement verification, reaching 79.94% F1-scores.
107	Systematic Review	Meta-analysis	Surveys NL-to-specification literature across domains and academic sources.
40	SAT-LLM	Neuro-symbolic (LLM + SMT)	Combines LLMs with SMT to detect complex conflicts in requirements.
32	Thor	Neuro-symbolic	Integrates LLMs with theorem provers using class methods like Hammers for proof completion.
67	Dafny Task Gen w/ CoT	Prompt + Retrieval + CoT	GPT-4 and PaLM-2 generate verified Dafny tasks via retrieval-augmented CoT prompting.
31	LeanDojo + ReProver	Retrieval-augmented	Retrieval-augmented LLM-based prover improves Lean theorem proving on 98K+ samples.
108	SynVer for C	Verifier-in-loop	Synthesizes and verifies C programs using VST with improved automation.
33	Copilot + Formal Methods	IDE Integration Proposal	Suggests integrating formal tools (e.g., Dafny, Coq, KeY) into IDEs like Copilot.
109	Robotic Systems Review	Meta-analysis	Reviews 10 years of literature on formal verification in autonomous robotic systems.
42	NLP for Software Dev	Survey / Meta-analysis	Evaluates NLP techniques in software development life cycle.
47	RML (1986)	Manual / Controlled NL	Introduces controlled NL framework for precise and consistent requirements writing.
103	ESBMC-AI	Neuro-symbolic	Uses LLMs + formal verification to detect vulnerabilities in software.
102	Specification Consistency Framework	Manual / Baseline	Aligns oral and formal specifications using semantic reasoning and input-output analysis.
110	LLM Safety Req. Pipeline	Prompt-only	Uses LLMs to decompose and refine autonomous vehicle safety requirements.
111	NLP Tools for TFM	Prompt-only	Compares NLP pipelines for topological modeling; CoreNLP and FreeLing perform best.

TABLE 7 Continued—Classification and Description of Surveyed Literature

Ref.	Tool / Work	Classification	Description
10	PALM (Proof-Aware LLM Method)	Verifier-in-loop + Repair Framework	Introduces PALM, a generatethenrepair framework combining large language models with symbolic reasoning to enhance formal proof generation in Coq. Analyzes 520 proof-generation errors by GPT-3.5 and introduces iterative repair mechanisms. Evaluated on 10,000+ theorems, achieving up to 180% higher success rates and proving 1,270 more theorems than prior systems, demonstrating strong generalizability.
11	AutoSpec	Fine-tuned + Verifier-in-loop	Presents AutoSpec, an automated framework synthesizing formal specifications that enables end-to-end program verification. Supports arrays, pointers, and nested loops via iterative synthesis and validation. Verifies 79% of benchmark programs (1.59E over existing methods) and validates real-world X509-parser project, ensuring satisfiable and provable specifications.
15	OntoChat	Conversational LLM for ORE	Introduces OntoChat, an LLM-powered conversational agent supporting Ontology Requirements Engineering (ORE). Automates and enhances tasks like elicitation, documentation, and validation in ontology development. Demonstrates improved efficiency, consistency, and collaboration compared to manual ORE pipelines.
16	HILBERT	Agentic + Neuro-symbolic Verification	Presents HILBERT, an integrated agentic framework combining informal reasoning, formal verification, and theorem proving. Coordinates reasoning agents, Lean 4 provers, and verifiers for collaborative proof construction. Achieves 99.2% accuracy on miniF2F and solves 70% of PutnamBench problems—surpassing proprietary and open baselines by large margins.
70	CLEVER Benchmark	Dataset / Benchmark	Introduces CLEVER, a benchmark for verifying code-level logical consistency in LLM-generated formal artifacts. Evaluates reasoning accuracy, specification completeness, and proof correctness across multiple verification engines.
71	CORE Dataset	Dataset / Benchmark	Provides CORE, a curated dataset linking natural-language software requirements to their formal counterparts in Dafny and Coq. Facilitates evaluation of NL-to-specification translation models for correctness and soundness.
73	VerifyThisBench	Benchmark / Evaluation	Presents VerifyThisBench, a comprehensive benchmark of 150+ verification problems. Measures LLM capabilities in producing provable Dafny, Coq, and Viper proofs, emphasizing stepwise reasoning and proof correctness.
43	DafnyBench	Dataset / Verifier-in-loop	Introduces DafnyBench, a large-scale benchmark for evaluating LLMs in generating and verifying Dafny specifications. Enables quantitative comparison of reasoning-based verification success rates.
22	RvLLM Framework	Verifier-in-loop + Runtime Verification	Combines runtime verification with LLM-based formalization to dynamically validate safety-critical behaviors in real-time systems. Integrates SMT-guided feedback for iterative correction.
34	Ada/SPARK-LLM Assistant	Verifier-in-loop + IDE Integration	Proposes LLM-assisted generation of Ada/SPARK contracts. Integrates within verification IDEs, enabling real-time correction of inconsistencies and generation of postconditions from natural language requirements.
35	GenAI-Driven Design-by-Contract	Prompt-only + Formal Spec Generation	Investigates how LLMs can automatically synthesize design-by-contract specifications in languages like Eiffel and SPARK from informal requirements, improving traceability and contract coverage.
74	ClassInvGen	Neuro-symbolic + Invariant Synthesis	Introduces ClassInvGen, a system for automatic generation of class invariants using hybrid symbolicLLM reasoning. Achieves 90% correctness in inferred invariants across benchmark programs.
24	PastLTL formulae	Prompt-only + Temporal Logic Translation	Presents a system for transforming natural language safety requirements into Past LTL formulae using LLM-guided semantic parsing, enabling temporal property verification.
25	LoopInvariantFinder	Prompt + Symbolic Refinement	Explores using GPT-4 and symbolic solvers to automatically infer loop invariants for C and Java programs. Achieves state-of-the-art generalization on the LoopInvGen dataset.
69	PURE Dataset	Dataset / Fine-tuned	Provides the PURE dataset mapping software requirements to Prolog-based logical rules, used to fine-tune LLMs for precise logic translation.
23	Farrel et al. 2025 Study	Meta-analysis / Empirical Review	Presents an empirical synthesis of model-based verification approaches leveraging LLMs and symbolic solvers across safety-critical domains.
100	Trustworthiness in LLM Verification Survey	Meta-analysis / Survey	Surveys approaches to evaluate and improve trustworthiness, interpretability, and safety of LLMs in software verification and formal reasoning contexts.
36	Barbosa et al. (2024) – JSS Review	Meta-analysis / Review	Reviews LLM-assisted formal verification frameworks in system design. Provides taxonomic classification of prompt-based, verifier-in-loop, and symbolic methods.
30	SV-LLM for SoC Verification	Domain-specific / Verifier-in-loop	Applies LLMs to SystemVerilog design verification tasks, generating functional assertions and testbench code. Demonstrates significant improvements in coverage for SoC-level validation.
16	HILBERT	Neuro-symbolic / Agentic Proof Framework	Integrates informal reasoning, formal verification, and theorem proving within an agentic architecture. Achieves SOTA results on formal mathematics benchmarks (miniF2F and PutnamBench).
75	Verina	Dataset / Verifier-in-loop	Comprising 189 manually curated coding tasks in Lean, each accompanied by precise problem statements, reference implementations, formal specifications, and exhaustive test suites. Evaluated dataset empirically.
76	CASP – C-ASCL Pairs	Dataset / Verifier-in-loop / Human-in-loop	introduced C-ASCL (CASP), a curated evaluation set comprising 506 C functions paired with ACSL specifications, constructed through a multi-stage extraction and verification pipeline.